

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part VIII: Toxoplasmosis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 213 primary studies investigating risk factors for sporadic infection with *Toxoplasma gondii*, which were conducted between 1983 and 2016. From these, eighteen studies investigated exposures in children/infants, thirty-seven in adults and seventy-eight in the mixed population, while ninety-seven studies focused on the susceptible population (predominantly pregnant women but also organ-transplanted people, elderly and the immunodeficient). These primary studies provided 2205 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 72% of the meta-analytical data produced by observational studies from Mexico (28 studies), Brazil (27), Iran (20), Ethiopia (13), USA (8), Egypt (6), Malaysia (6), Taiwan (6), China (5), UK (5), France (4), Saudi Arabia (4) and Thailand (4). Two-hundred and eight primary studies (~97.7%) employed an unmatched experimental design and produced a total of 2109 ORs. From these, 1421 reported or computed ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (i.e., crude ORs), while the others were adjusted by using either unconditional logistic regressions (675 ORs) or Mantel-Haenzel method (13 ORs). On the other hand, only five studies (~2.3%) employed a matched experimental design, providing for meta-analysis a total of 96 ORs. From these, most of them were adjusted by the Mantel-Haenzel method (61 ORs) or logistic regressions (27 ORs). After methodological quality assessment, fifteen primary studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 162 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (1983 ORs) than on host specific factors (200) and travel (22).

According to this meta-analysis study, host-specific factors, as a whole, represented the most important set of risk factors for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the three population types: mixed (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.12), children (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.01 – 2.57) and susceptible (overall OR=1.87; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.40). In the mixed population, certain food categories, namely, seafood (overall OR=1.79; 95% CI: 1.02 – 3.14), produce (overall

OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.49 – 2.14) and meats (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.54 – 1.99) posed at least an equivalent risk of toxoplasmosis as the animal-related pathways of transmission (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.48 – 1.99), yet a discernably higher risk than the environmental pathways as a whole (overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 1.39 – 1.70). A comparable global trend was observed in the susceptible population whereby consumption of meat (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.52 – 1.99) conveyed a higher risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis than animal related pathways (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.49 – 1.83), followed by environmental routes (overall OR=1.56; 95% CI: 1.38 – 1.76). However, in children, the opposite occurred: the environmental pathways (overall OR=1.70; 95% CI: 1.33 – 2.17) and contact with animals (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.28 – 1.96) were more important vehicles of transmission than foods as a whole (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.63).

In the mixed population, the most important determinants of toxoplasmosis, as disaggregated sources, were: poor hygiene habits (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.13 – 5.85), suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.55), occupational contact with animals (overall OR=2.01; 95% CI: 1.65 – 2.45) and contact with soil (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.49 – 2.51). In the mixed population, consumption of foods such as raw molluscs (only Asian; overall OR=1.95; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.65), pork (overall OR=1.84; 95% CI: 1.32 – 2.55), fresh vegetables (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.48 – 2.22), red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.42 – 2.30), raw/rare beef/non-specific meats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.45 – 2.12), unwashed fruits and vegetables (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.37 – 2.24) and other meats (overall OR=1.73; 95% CI: 1.52 – 1.97) presented a level of risk of toxoplasmosis comparable (if not, higher) to that of the most known source of toxoplasmosis, contact with cats (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.53 – 1.94) or pets in general (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.45 – 1.96). At a lower mean association with toxoplasmosis laid the environmental routes of untreated drink water (overall OR=1.68; 95% CI: 1.28 – 2.19), farm environment (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.25 – 2.14) and exposure to waste water or human waste (overall OR=1.55; 95% CI: 0.85 – 2.84); followed by other animal-related pathways, such as contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.47; 95% CI: 1.19 – 1.81) and farm animals (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.00). Food vehicles found to pose a lower mean risk of transmission of toxoplasmosis were: beef meat, mostly undercooked (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.00), poultry meat (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.03), unwashed fruits (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.84 – 2.24), raw milk (overall OR=1.27; 95% CI: 1.03 – 1.58) and processed meat (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.93 – 1.65).

In children, the top three most important risk factors were: consumption of rare pork/cured meat (overall OR=2.19; 95% CI: 1.34 – 5.85), keeping poor hygiene habits (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 0.82 – 5.17) – a top factor also encountered in the mixed population – and living on a farm (overall OR=2.02; 95% CI: 1.70 – 2.39), all of which posed a higher level of risk than the best known source of toxoplasmosis, contact with cats (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.31 – 2.03) or any pet (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.07). Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children were: exposure to human waste (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.34 – 1.83), suffering from medical conditions (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.91 – 2.52), contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.87), other (non-classifiable) meats (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 0.94 – 2.08), untreated drink water (overall OR=1.38; 95% CI: 1.20 – 1.59), contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.81) and contact with soil (overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.30).

In the susceptible population, the top three determinants of toxoplasmosis were: suffering from a medical condition (overall OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.76 – 3.00), consuming beef – mostly undercooked (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.44 – 3.09) and being exposed to waste water or human waste (overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.18 – 3.01). Consuming red meats, mostly of wild nature (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.31 – 2.65) was as unsafe an eating habit in pregnant women as consuming any raw/rare meat (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.52 – 2.14), while having occupational contact with animals (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.44) was as risky as having contact with cats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.57 – 1.97). Consuming other (non-classifiable) meats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.50 – 2.06), living on a farm (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.15), and having contact with any pet (overall OR=1.66; 95% CI: 1.46 – 1.87) were at least as strong determinants of toxoplasmosis as international travel (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.53), pork meat (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.53), unwashed fruits and vegetables (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.20 – 2.17), poultry meat (overall OR=1.60; 95% CI: 1.08 – 2.37), processed meats (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.32), fruits (overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.22) and contact with soil (overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.33 – 1.66) in the susceptible population. Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in susceptible people, although at a lesser association, were: consumption of raw eggs (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.22), suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=1.42; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.12), drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 1.21 – 1.61), contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.95), and consumption of raw milk (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI: 1.07 – 1.67) and vegetables (overall OR=1.30; 95% CI: 1.13 – 1.49). Unlike the mixed population, composite dishes eaten out represented a risky practice in the susceptible population (overall OR=1.23; 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.63).

Other meta-analysis models were adjusted to estimate the effects of food handling (i.e., raw, undercooked, unwashed) on the pooled ORs in selected food categories. It was found that people who ate raw meat had on average 1.253 times (95% CI: 0.996 – 1.576) greater probability of acquiring toxoplasmosis than those who stated having consumed *simply* meat. However, when meat was undercooked, the odds of infection increased only marginally by ~1.084 (95% CI: 0.897 – 1.313). On the other hand, not washing vegetables before consumption increased the risk of toxoplasmosis by 1.465 (95% CI: 1.179 – 1.820), which was significantly higher than that of eating vegetables in raw state (risk increased by 1.157; 95% CI: 0.905 – 1.480). Consuming raw milk or raw milk cheese also conveyed an increased risk of toxoplasmosis, quantified as 1.414 times (95% CI: 1.062 – 1.850) that of consuming milk/cheese. In the mixed population, routes of exposures likely to be minor or non-significant sources of toxoplasmosis were: person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 0.57 – 4.73), recreational water (overall OR=1.33; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.59), milk products (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.81), raw eggs (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.00), fish (overall OR=1.04; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.41), composite dishes (overall OR=0.93; 95% CI: 0.52 – 1.67), domestic travel (overall OR=0.89; 95% CI: 0.69 – 1.15) and international travel (overall OR=0.69; 95% CI: 0.48 – 1.00); while, in children, the least important routes were all related to food pathways; namely: red meats including beef (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 0.57 – 2.84), milk (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.78 – 1.97), raw/rare meats (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.66 – 2.26), raw vegetables (overall OR=0.87; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.03) and poultry meat (overall OR=0.73; 95% CI: 0.28 – 1.92). Finally, minor risk factors for toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population were: recent use of antibiotics (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.63 – 2.51), consuming cheese (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.61 – 1.58), contact with farm animals (overall OR=0.93; 95% CI: 0.67 – 1.31) and exposure to recreational water (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.53 – 1.03).

3. Results

3.8 *Toxoplasma gondii*

3.8.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors for human infection with *Toxoplasma gondii*, a total of 1640 clean bibliographic sources were identified using appropriate keywords in the five search engines, from which 217 cohort and case-control studies passed the full assessment for eligibility (Figure 1). From these, four fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. Meta-analysis was undertaken on data either extracted or calculated from 213 primary studies – cohort and case-control studies – focusing on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted in years spanning from 1983 and 2016. Table 1 compiles a list of the primary studies along with their main features. The eligible studies jointly provided 2205 odds-ratios categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 412 ORs were retrieved from 37 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 1793 ORs were excerpted from 176 case-control studies performed after 2000. Meta-analytical data were obtained from primary studies conducted in 65 countries, although studies from only 13 countries provided ~72% of the ORs retrieved. These were: Mexico (28 studies), Brazil (27), Iran (20), Ethiopia (13), USA (8), Egypt (6), Malaysia (6), Taiwan (6), China (5), UK (5), France (4), Saudi Arabia (4) and Thailand (4) (Figure 2, top).

Primary studies investigated risk factors in different types of population, namely children (18 studies), adults (37 studies) and mixed population (78 studies). Other 97 primary studies were conducted on immunodeficient patients, solid organ transplant recipients, elderly people, patients with chronic diseases and pregnant women, which were all grouped into the susceptible population. However, the susceptible population was predominantly embodied by pregnant women as these were subject of investigation in 81 out of 97 primary studies; and hence, it should be noted that pooled ORs meta-analysed for the susceptible population will be more representative of pregnant females. The adult population data (327 ORs) was incorporated to the mixed population data (703 ORs); and separate meta-analyses were then adjusted on the mixed (1030 ORs), susceptible (989 ORs) and children population (186 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom left). Only when the observations within a data partition (i.e., subset for a risk factor or pathway) were too few, the meta-analysis model was fitted to the whole subset without distinction of population type. In primary studies, the toxoplasmosis cases were diagnosed by routine antibody screening for *T. gondii* IgG and/or IgM antibodies (Figure 3).

Only five case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 96 categorised ORs, which represented 4.3% of the data. Of these, 15 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis whereas 81 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using MH (61) and conditional logistic regression (27), while only a few by the simple chi-square test (5) and the unconditional logistic regression (3). From the studies that applied an unmatched design (208 studies), mostly cohort studies, a total of 2109 ORs were extracted or calculated, which constituted 95.7% of the meta-analytical data. A total of 1607 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 502 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (1421) and UL (675) whilst only 13 ORs were MH-estimates adjusted by a confounding variable. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 1595 ORs (72.3% of the data) were

not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 610 ORs (27.7%) were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for cohort and case-control studies of human toxoplasmosis

*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from cohort and case-control studies of sporadic human toxoplasmosis by country (top), population type (bottom right) and pathway of exposure (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from cohort and case-control studies of sporadic human toxoplasmosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period with cut-off year 2000 (bottom left) and serological diagnosis (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of the 213 primary studies investigating risk factors for acquiring toxoplasmosis included in the meta-analysis

StudyID	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model	# ill/ non-ill	Quality # Final ORs/ Removed*
Abamecha and Awel 2016	Ethiopia	Dec 2014 - Feb 2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni -UL Multi-UL	198 ill 34 non-ill	Good 10
Abu et al. 2015	Ghana	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni -Chi	333 ill 57 non-ill	Good 16/3
Abu et al. 2016	Ghana	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	333 ill 308 non-ill	Good 5/1
Adesiyum et al. 2011	Trinidad	Apr - Jun 2006	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	194 ill 299 non-ill	Poor 1
Adesiyum et al. 2007	Trinidad	Nov 2002 - Sep 2003	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	206 ill 270 non-ill	Good 6
Agmas et al. 2015	Ethiopia	Feb - May 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	180 ill 83 non-ill	Good 8
Ahmed et al. 2014	Egypt	Dec 2013 - Mar 2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	73 ill 27 non-ill	Good 11/1
Akoijam et al. 2002	India	Aug 1996 - Sep 1997	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni -Chi	210 ill 294 non-ill	Good 9
Al-Eryani et al. 2016	Yemen	Dec 2010 - Apr 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	268 ill 325 non-ill	Good 8
Al-Hamdani and Mahdi 1997	Iraq	Oct 1994 - May 1995	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	22 ill 178 non-ill	Good 1
Almushait et al. 2012	Saudi Arabia	Jan 2008 Aug 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	189 ill 418 non-ill	Good 14
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2006a	Mexico	Dec 2005 - Mar 2006	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni Multi UL	41 ill 276 non-ill 25 ill 112 non-ill	Good 8/1
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2015a	Mexico	Nov 2003 - Aug 2014	Susceptible Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Uni- Chi Uni- Chi	15 ill 134 non-ill 14 ill 135 non-ill 15 ill 134 non-ill	Good 24/4
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2011a	Mexico	Dec 2009 - Nov 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni - Chi Multi-UL	46 ill 554 non-ill	Good 18
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2016a	Mexico	Oct 2014 - Feb 2016	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi -UL	21 ill 314 non-ill	Good 21/8
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2014c	Mexico	Aug 2013 - Jul 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	23 ill 377 non-ill	Poor 23/5
Alvarado et al. 2014a	Mexico	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	35 ill 131 non-ill	Poor 8
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2016b	Mexico	Sep - Nov 2016	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	29 ill 375 non-ill	Good 23/3
Alvarado - Esquivel et al. 2011b	Mexico	Jan 2009 - May 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	59 ill 911 non-ill	Good 28/2
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2011c	Mexico	Sep 2009 - Oct 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	9 ill 154 non-ill	Poor 21
Alvarado - Esquivel et al. 2011d	Mexico	Jan 2009 - Dec 2010	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni Chi Uni- Chi	26 ill 134 non-ill 10 ill	Good 25/2

					Multi-UL	65 non-ill	
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2012b	Mexico	Jan 2009 - Dec 2010	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	11 ill 122 non-ill	Good 11/3
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2013	Mexico	Aug 2010 - Aug 2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni Multi-UL	50 ill 123 non-ill	Poor 29/5
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2014b	Mexico	Set 2013 - Jan 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	71 ill 143 non-ill	Good 19
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2015b	Mexico	Nov 2013 - July 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	23 ill 169 non-ill	Good 9
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2008	Mexico	May - Set 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	25 ill 147 non-ill	Poor 11
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2006b	Mexico	Jul 2005 - Mar 2006	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	21 ill 321 non-ill	Good 19
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2015c	Mexico	Aug 2013 - Jan 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	14 ill 136 non-ill	Good 23
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2016c	Mexico	Dec 2015- Aug 2016	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni Multi-UL	130 ill 245non-ill	Good 20/10
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2016d	Mexico	Aug 2015- Feb 2016	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	33 ill 292 non-ill	Good 1
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2009	Mexico	Aug 2007- Feb 2008	Susceptible	Unmatched	Multi-UL	36 ill 403 non-ill	Good 7
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2010a	Mexico	Jul 2008- Aug 2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	30 ill 398 non-ill	Poor 3
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2010b	Mexico	Jun 2009- Jan 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	46 ill 108 non-ill	Good 34/6
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2011e	Mexico	Jan 2009 - Jun 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	18 ill 182 non-ill	Good 2
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2014d	Mexico	Nov 2011- Sep 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	17 ill 275 non-ill	Good 1
Alvarado-Esquivel et al. 2012a	Mexico	Nov 2006 - Mar 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	58 ill 425 non-ill	Good 30
Andiappan et al. 2014b	Malaysia	2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	159 ill 275 non-ill	Good 8
Andiappan et al. 2014a	Thailand	Dec 2012 - Aug 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	190 ill 570 non-ill	Good 11
Angal et al. 2016	Malaysia	2012	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	127 ill 176 non-ill 84 ill 49 non-ill	Good 8
Athari et al. 1994	Iran	1991- 1992	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	162 ill 333 non-ill	Good 1
Avelino et al. 2004	Brazil	1997- 1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	1148 ill 1094 non-ill	Good 10
Avelino et al. 2003	Brazil	Jan 1997 - 1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	68 ill 1046 non-ill	Good 10
Awoke et al. 2015	Ethiopia	Nov 2013 - Jan 2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	71 ill 313 non-ill	Good 13

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Ayi et al. 2016	Ghana	2016	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	64 ill 61 non-ill	Good 8
Babaie et al. 2013	Iran	Feb 2010 - Jan 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	144 ill 275 non-ill	Good 4
Barbosa et al. 2009	Brazil	Mar - Dec 2007	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	127 ill 63 non-ill	Good 13/1
Baril et al. 1999	France	1995	Susceptible	Matched	Uni- Chi Uni- MH Multi-CL	80 ill 80 non-ill	Good 29
Bittencourt et al. 2012	Brazil	Jul 2009 - Out 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	213 ill 143 non-ill	Good 14/1
Bobic et al. 1998	Serbia	1988- 1991	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	896 ill 261 non-ill	Good 3
Bobic et al. 2010	Serbia	Apr 2004- Mar 2008	Mixed	Matched	Uni-UL	34 ill 357 non-ill	Good 1
Bobic et al. 2016	Bosnia	Feb 2015	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	98 ill 222 non-ill	Good 2
Brandon et al. 2015	Malaysia	Oct 2013- Apr 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	62 ill 250 non-ill	Poor 11
Buery et al. 2014	Brazil	2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	51 ill 25 non-ill	Good 13/2
Buffolano et al. 1996	Italy	Nov 1991 - Jun 1994	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	1422 ill 2096 non-ill	Good 16
Caiaffa et al. 1993	Brazil	1985	Children Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Uni- Chi	340 ill 5050 non-ill 451 ill 400 non-ill	Good 10
Camara et al. 2015	Brazil	Jul 2011- Dec 2012	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	437 ill 124 non-ill	Good 22
Camargo et al. 1995	Brazil	Jun 1983- Jan 1984	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	297 ill 203 non-ill	Good 5
Carellas et al. 2014	Brazil	Nov 2006 - May 2007	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Uni-UL Multi-UL	175 ill 278 non-ill	Good 31
Cavalcante et al. 2006	Brazil	May-Oct 2002	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	195 ill 71 non-ill	Poor 9
Chandrasena et al. 2016	Sri Lanka	Feb- Jun 2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	36 ill 257 non-ill	Good 14
Chemoh et al. 2015	Thailand	Oct 2009- Jun 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	109 ill 191 non-ill	Good 6
Chiang et al. 2012	Taiwan	Jun- Oct2010	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	167 ill 1615 non-ill	Good 26
Chiang et al. 2014	Taiwan	2008-2013	Adult	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	30 ill 224 non-ill	Good 16
Chiaretta et al. 2003	Argentina	1999 -2001	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	133 ill 124 non-ill	Good 6
Chintana et al. 1998	Thailand	Jul-Dec 1996	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-Chi	330 ill 1043non-ill	Good 4
Cong et al. 2015b	China	Oct 2011- Jul2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	314 ill 1616 non-ill	Good 15
Cong et al. 2015a	China	Jul 2012- Feb2014	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-Chi Multi-UL	519 ill 1281non-ill	Good 19
Cook et al. 2000	West	Jan 1994 -	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL	253 ill	Good

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	Europe	Jun1995			Multi-UL	858 non-ill	47
Cvetkovic et al. 2010	Macedonia	Jan 2004-Dec2005	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	48ill 187 non-ill	Good 3
Dattoli et al. 2011	West Europe	1997-2003	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	213 ill 1004 non-ill	Good 10
Decavalas et al. 1990	Macedonia	Set 1986-Jul 1987	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	154 ill 149 non-ill	Good 4
Del Castillo and Herruzo 1998	Spain	1997	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	311 ill 416 non-ill	Good 7
Domingos et al. 2013	Mozambique	Jul-Dec2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	54 ill 166 non-ill	Good 3
Doni et al. 2015	Turkey	Jan-Apr 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	399 ill 285non-ill	Poor 2
Gómez-Martin et al. 2012	Colombia	2011	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	394 ill 295 non-ill	Good 17/1
El-Nawawy et al. 1996	Egypt	Apr 1992-1993	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	67 ill 83 non-ill	Good 1
Elsafi et al. 2015	Saudi Arabia	Sep 2012-Oct 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	114 ill 286 non-ill	Good 8
Elsheikha et al. 2009	Egypt	Mar- Sep 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	155ill 75 non-ill	Good 11
Endris et al. 2014	Ethiopia	May 2010-Oct 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	341 ill 44 non-ill	Good 18
Ertug et al. 2005	Turkey	2004	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	110 ill 272 non-ill	Good 13/1
Etheredge et al. 2004	Panama	1991	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	94 ill 665 non-ill	Good 2
Fakhfakh et al. 2013	France	Mar 2010 - Fev 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	1121ill 1230 non-ill	Good 5
Fallah et al. 2008	Iran	2004	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	193 ill 383 non-ill	Good 6/1
Fan et al. 2001	Taiwan	Jul 1999-Jun2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	190 ill 503 non-ill	Good 14
Fan et al. 2002	Taiwan	Feb1998-Jul200	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	246 ill 793 non-ill	Good 2
Fan et al. 2012	São Tomé	Oct 2010	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	158 ill 88 non-ill	Good 4
Fernandez-Sabé et al. 2012	Spain	Jan 2000 - Dec 2009	Susceptible	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	22 ill 44 non-ill	Good 6
Ferreira et al. 2014	Brazil	2009 - 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	260 ill 89 non-ill	Good 10
Flatt and Shetty 2013	UK	2006 - 2008	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	452 ill 2158 non-ill	Good 8
Frenkel et al. 1995	Panama	Aug 1987 Jul 1992	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	72 ill 499 non-ill	Good 20/5
Frimpong et al. 2017	Zambia	Aug - Out 2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	24 ill 387 non-ill	Good 8/1
Fromont et al. 2008	France	Mar - Sep 2004	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	128 ill 145 non-ill	Good 14
Fu et al. 2014	Marshall	2013	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	91 ill 75 non-ill	Good 4
Galvan et al. 1995	Mexico	1995	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	107 ill 27 non-ill	Good 8/2
Gamba et al. 2013	Central African	Nov 2011-Jan 2012	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	221 ill 213 non-ill	Good 1
Garcia et al. 2003	Brazil	1997-1999	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- MH	822 ill	Good

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					Multi-UL	614 non-ill	18/2
Garcia et al. 2004	Brazil	2001	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	438 ill 513 non-ill	Good 7
Gebremedhin et al. 2013	Ethiopia	Mar - Sep 2011	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	448 ill 87 non-ill	Good 20
Gelaye et al. 2015	Ethiopia	Nov 2010 - Jan 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	246 ill 42 non-ill	Good 10
Gyang et al. 2015	Nigeria	Nov 2013- Mar 2014	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	91 ill 291 non-ill	Poor 20
Hamza et al. 2015	Egypt	2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	76 ill 44 non-ill	Good 6
Han et al. 2008	Korea	Dec 2005- Aug 2006	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	13 ill 338 non-ill	Good 5
Hernandez-Cortazar et al. 2016	Mexico	Sep 2013 - Jun 2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	944 ill 65 non-ill	Good 18/2
Hofhuis et al. 2011	Netherlands	1995-1996 and 2006-2007	Mixed Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	3157 ill 4364 non-ill 193 ill 2251 non-ill	Good 6
Hung et al. 2015	Taiwan	Sep 2009- Feb 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL	7 ill 9 non-ill	Good 5
Hung et al. 2007	SaoTome	Nov 2003- Mar 2004	Susceptible	Unmatched	Multi-UL	366 ill 128 non-ill	Good 4
Jafari et al. 2012	Iran	2008	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	60 ill 110 non-ill	Good 5
James et al. 2013	Nigeria	Oct 2011- Dec 2012	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	68 ill 212 non-ill	Good 2
Jimenez-Coello et al. 2011	Mexico	Jan - May 2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	29 ill 60 non-ill	8/1
John et al. 2012	Papua New Guinea	Mar 2003- 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	157 ill 144 non-ill	Good 3
Jones et al. 2005	Guatemala	Sep - Dec 1999	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	172 ill 466 non-ill	Good 57
Jones et al. 2001	USA	1988-1994	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi - UL Uni-Chi	3964 ill 13679 non-ill	Good 3
Jones et al. 2009	USA	Aug 2002- May 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	148 ill 413 non-ill	Good 9
Jones et al. 2006	Brazil	Jun 2003- 2004	Mixed Adult Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL Uni-Chi Multi-UL Uni-Chi Multi-UL	131 ill 110 non-ill 46 ill 40 non-ill 58 ill 48 non-ill	Good 28/2
Juanah et al. 2013	Malaysia	2012	Adult Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL Multi-UL	72 ill 104 non-ill 45 ill 43 non-ill	Good 17/3
Jumaian 2005	Jordan	Jan 2000 - May 2001	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	132 ill 148 non-ill	Good 4
Kamal et al. 2015	Egypt	Apr. 2013- 2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	71 ill 169 non-ill	Good 4
Kamani et al. 2009	Nigeria	Feb- May 2008	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	35 ill 126 non-ill	Good 4
Kapperud et al. 1996	Norway	Jun 1992 - 1994	Susceptible	Matched	Uni- MH Multi- CL	63 ill 128 non-ill 63 ill 123 non-ill	Good 44/3

Karabulut et al. 2015	Turkey	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	63 ill 82 non-ill	Good 1
Kareshk et al. 2016	Iran	Jan - Apr 2015	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	32 ill 293 non-ill	Good 10
Khazaei et al. 2011	Iran	Jan - May 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	15 ill 245 non-ill	Good 3
Khazaei et al. 2012	Iran	Feb - Dec2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	80 ill 200 non-ill	Good 2/1
Kheirandish et al. 2016	Iran	2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	168 ill 318 non-ill	Good 26/1
Kolbekova et al. 2007	Czech Rep	Apr 2000- Sep 2004	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	757 ill 2533 non-ill	Good 4
Kortbeek et al. 2004	Netherlands	Oct 1995- Dec 1996	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	348 ill 1978 non-ill	Good 10
Krueger et al. 2014	USA	1999- 2004 and 2009- 2010	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- UL Multi- UL	2639 ill 20383 non-ill	Good 8
Kumari et al. 2011	Nepal	2010	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	8 ill 16 non-ill	Poor 1
Laboudi et al. 2009	Morocco	2008	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	490 ill 530 non-ill	Good 3
Li et al. 2015	China	Mar- Dec 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	248 ill 902 non-ill	Good 4
Liassides et al. 2016	Cyprus	2008-2011	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	54 ill 800 non-ill	Good 11
Lin et al. 2008	Taiwan	2007	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	131 ill 291 non-ill	Good 11/2
Lobo et al. 2017	Portugal	Apr 2010- Jan 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	31 ill	Good 23
	Angola	Oct-Nov 2011			Multi- UL Uni- Chi Multi- UL	101 non-ill 82 ill 217 non-ill	
Lopes et al. 2012	Portugal	Jan2009- Dec 2010	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi- UL	99 ill 3030 non-ill	Good 13/1
Lopes et al. 2009	Brazil	May-Dec 2006	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	242 ill 250 non-ill	Good 8
Lopes et al. 2008	Brazil	2007	Children	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	65 ill 1010 non-ill	Good 6/1
Lopes-Mori et al. 2013	Brazil	2007-2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	1145 ill 10 89 non-ill	Good 8
Lopez-Castillo et al. 2005	Colombia	Sep 2004- Feb2005	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	14 ill 34 non-ill	Good 6
Macknight and Robinson 1992	USA	1992	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	63 ill 84 non-ill	Good 3
Majid et al. 2016	Pakistan	2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	135 ill 598 non-ill	Good 9
Marchioro et al. 2015	Brazil	Dec2009- Jun2011	Children	Unmatched	Multi- UL	40 ill 504 non-ill	Good 3
Mardani and Tavalla 2015	Iran	2014	Adult	Unmatched	Uni	79 ill 47 non-ill	Good 1
Markovich et al. 2014	Israel	2006-2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	351 ill 1462 non-ill	Good 3
Markovitz et al. 2015	USA	2008-2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	128 ill 356 non-ill	Good 7
Martinez-Sánchez et al. 1991	Cuba	1985	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	159 ill 125 non-ill	Good 4
Meng et al. 2015	China	May 2013- Jul 2014	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	197 ill 1303 non-ill	Good 27
Messier et al. 2009	Canada	Sep 2004	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	548 ill 369 non-ill	Good 5

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Messerer et al. 2014	Algeria	Jan 2006- Dec 2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Multi-UL	209 ill 281 non-ill	Good 3
Millar et al. 2007	Brazil	Nov 2004- feb 2005	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	99 ill 75 non-ill	Good 6
Minbaeva et al. 2013	Kyrgyzstan	2008-2009	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	66 ill 996 non-ill	Good 8
Mohamed et al. 2016	Saudi Arabia	Apr- Aug2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	69 ill 269 non-ill	Good 18/3
Mohammad et al. 2010	Saudi Arabia	2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	285 ill 252 non-ill	Good 8
Mohammad et al. 1998	United Arab Emirates	Jan- May1995	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	317 ill 614 non-ill	Good 2
Mostafavi et al. 2011	Iran	2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	248 ill 349 non-ill	Good 1
Moura et al. 2013	Brazil	Sep 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	234 ill 166 non-ill	Good 10
Munoz-Zanzi et al. 2016	Chile	Aug 2010- Mar 2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	213 ill 150 non-ill	Good 6
Mwambe et al. 2013	Tanzania	Nov 2012- Mar2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	109 ill 241 non-ill	Good 4/1
Nash et al. 2005	UK	Oct 1999- Nov 2001	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi- UL	172 ill 1721 non-ill	Good 62
Negash et al. 2008	Ethiopia	Nov1999- Mar2000	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	39 ill 26 non-ill	Good 2
Nejad et al. 2011a	Iran	2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	273 ill 554 non-ill	Good 1
Nejad et al. 2011b	Iran	2008-2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	250 ill 471 non-ill	Good 6
Nimri et al. 2004	France	2004	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	92 ill 156 non-ill	Good 1
Nissapatorn et al. 2011	Thailand	Oct 2009- Jun2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi Multi-UL	181 ill 459 non-ill	Good 10/1
Nissapatorn et al. 2003	Malaysia	Jan 2002- Mar 2002	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni - Chi Multi-UL	98 ill 102 non-ill	Good 6/2
Nissapatorn et al. 2002	Malaysia	2002	Mixed Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni - Chi	78 ill 225 non-ill 51 ill 133 non-ill	Good 6/2
Njunda et al. 2011b	Cameroon	May -Jun 2008	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	72 ill 38 non-ill	Good 3
Njunda et al. 2011a	Cameroon	Mar - Jul 2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	77 ill 33 non-ill	Good 4
Obaidat et al. 2015	Jordan	Sep 2013 - Jul 2014	Adult	Unmatched	Multi-UL	134 ill 68 non-ill	Good 1
Oskouei et al. 2016	Iran	2014	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	132 ill 18 non-ill	Good 3
Perez et al. 1992	Spain	1992	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	237 ill 206 non-ill	Good 1
Perry et al. 2016	USA	2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	81 ill 138 non-ill	Good 1
Radon et al. 2004	Germany	Apr - Aug 2002	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Uni-Chi Multi- UL	98 ill 223 non-ill	Good 14
Rashno et al. 2016	Iran	Jul 2014- Jan 2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi- UL	107 ill 67 non-ill	Good 4

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Retmanasari et al. 2017	Indonesia	2014	Adult	Unmatched	Uni- Chi	394 ill 236 non-ill	Good 7
Rey and Ramalho 1999	Brazil	1997	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	531 ill 464 non-ill	Good 1
Rocha et al. 2015	Brazil	2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	230 ill 110 non-ill	Good 9
Rodrigues et al. 2015	Brazil	2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	25 ill 87 non-ill	Good 4/1
Rostami et al. 2016	Iran	Jul 2014- Mar2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	477 ill 153 non-ill	Poor 16
Sadaghian et al. 2014	Iran	2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	88 ill 107 non-ill	Good 5
Sadaghian and Jafari 2016	Iran	2014	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	56 ill 104 non-ill	Good 1
Said et al. 2017	UK	Dec 2012- 2013	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	28 ill 27 non-ill	Good 26
Salamon and Bulanda 2014	Poland	Jan 2013- Mar2014	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	26 ill 52 non-ill	Good 2
Sang-Eun et al. 2013	Korea	2009	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	42 ill 606 non-ill	Good 27/1
Santos et al. 2009	Brazil	2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	133 ill 3 non-ill	Good 3
Sari et al. 2015	Indonesia	2009-2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	207 ill 479 non-ill	Poor 6
Seuri and Kosela 1992	Finland	1989	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	53 ill 121 non-ill	Good 3
Sharbatkhori et al. 2014	Iran	Set2012- Oct2012	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-UL	221 ill 536 non-ill	Good 14
Shiadeh et al. 2016	Iran	Jun2014- Jan2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni	194 ill 54 non-ill	Good 1
Shimelis et al. 2009	Ethiopia	Jan 2007- Feb 2007	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	297 ill 33non-ill	Good 5
Shirbazou et al. 2013	Iran	2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	91 ill 93 non-ill	Poor 1
Siddiqui et al. 2014	India	Fev 2011 Sep 2012	Mixed	Matched	Uni-Chi	40 ill 71 non-ill	Poor 9/1
Silva et al. 2014	Brazil	Fev 2012- Jun 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Multi-UL Uni-Chi	322 ill 151 non-ill	Good 40/1
Sroka et al. 2010	Brazil	Feb-May 2005	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni Multi-UL	661 ill 302 non-ill	Good 27
Studenicova et al. 2008	Slovakia	2008	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	145 ill 511 non-ill	Good 1
Studenicova et al. 2006	Slovakia	Jan - Oct 2003	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	113 ill 323 non-ill	Good 1
Sucilathangam and Anna 2016	India	2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	46 ill 306 non-ill	Good 5
Sultana et al. 2014	Bangladesh	Dec 2008- Nov 2009	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	15 ill 76 non-ill	Good 2
Swai and Schoonman 2009	Tanzania	Nov 2005	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	91 ill 108 non-ill	Good 3
Tammam et al. 2013	Egypt	Jan 2012- Mar 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	35 ill 41 non-ill	Poor 2
Tawfeeq et al. 2012	Iraq	Oct 2009- Feb 2010	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	61 ill 214 non-ill	Good 9
Tegegne et al. 2016	Ethiopia	Feb-Mar 2015	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	109 ill 26 non-ill	Good 7/1
Tilahun et al. 2016	Ethiopia	Apr- Set 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	233 ill 121 non-ill	Good 16

Thaller et al. 2011	Italy	Jan - Dec 2005	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	113 ill 1679 non-ill	Good 9
			Susceptible			90 ill 92 non-ill	Good 18/2
Walle et al. 2013	Ethiopia	2013	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi -UL	71 ill 98 non-ill	
Wam et al. 2016	Cameroon	Aug - Dec 2014	Susceptible Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	44 ill 78 non-ill 97 ill 81 non-ill	Good 15
Weigel et al. 1999	USA	1992- 1993	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	54 ill 120 non-ill	Poor 15/1
Wilking et al. 2016	Germany	2008-2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	3499 ill 3688 non-ill	Good 7
Yobi et al. 2012	Congo	May- Jun2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	627 ill 154 non-ill	Good 8
Yohanes et al. 2014	Ethiopia	Apr - Jun 2013	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	150 ill 20 non-ill	Good 9/2
Yusuf et al. 2016	Nigeria	Jan - Dec 2014	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	93 ill 264 non-ill	Good 7
Zhang et al. 2016	China	Jun 2013- Aug2015	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	98 ill 704 non-ill	Good 16
Zemene et al. 2012	Ethiopia	Aug-Set 2011	Susceptible	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	168 ill 33non-ill	Good 8
Zanzi et al. 2013	USA	1997-1999	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	37ill 305 non-ill	Good 2

(*) Number of ORs not included in the meta-analysis for presenting mean values lower than 0.50.

During methodological quality assessment, fifteen cohort studies were marked as being possibly affected by bias (Table 1). Potential for selection bias was assigned to thirteen cohort studies whose population groups were believed to have a stronger exposure to *Toxoplasma gondii* infection, such as waste pickers and waste workers (Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2008; Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2010a), livestock and abattoir workers (Adeyisum et al., 2011; Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2011c; Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2014c), agricultural workers or rural people living in poverty (Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2013; Cavalcante et al., 2013; Doni et al., 2015; Rostami et al., 2016), veterinary practitioners (Brandon-Mong et al., 2015), immates (Alvarado-Esquivel et al., 2014a; Sari et al., 2015), and female patients with miscarriages (Tammam et al., 2013). The rationale for assigning potential-for-bias status to the association measures extracted from Gyang et al. (2015) related to the statistical approach employed, which was a log-binomial model producing prevalence ratio estimates. The outcome measures from Kumari et al. (2001) were assigned potential-for-bias status because of the very small sample size they employed. The aforementioned primary studies provided 162 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the pooled ORs was evaluated by means of the Cook's distance.

With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (1983 ORs) than on host specific factors (200 ORs) or travel (22 ORs). Within the diverse pathways of transmission (90% of the meta-analytical data), the food consumption pathways (46.5%) and animal-related routes (27.6%) had the greatest share (Figure 2, bottom right). General information on the distribution of the number

of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and serological diagnosis.

3.8.2 Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal-, food-related and person-to-person pathways of transmission

The association measures of toxoplasmosis with most of its risk factors and pathways of transmission have not changed significantly in recent years, as implied by the non-significant effect of study period on the pooled ORs. Study period was found to be influential only in the meta-analyses on travel in the susceptible population ($p=0.001$; Table 2B), overall environmental pathways in children ($p=0.116$; Table 5B) and overall food pathways in children ($p=0.018$; Table 7B). As suggested by those meta-analyses, in earlier years, children were more prone to acquire toxoplasmosis through general environmental pathways (~ 1.2 times = $\exp(0.168)$ in Table 5B), yet less prone to acquire the disease through the food pathways (~ 1.9 times = $1/\exp(-0.427)$ in Table 7B) than in recent years. Furthermore, before the year 2000, the susceptible population were on average ~ 2.2 times ($\exp(0.772)$ in Table 2B) more likely to become infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* following international travel than in recent years (Table 2B).

The meta-analysis on travel by geographical region suggested that in South America, travel is not an important risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (pooled OR=0.858; $p=0.138$ in Table 2A). Nonetheless, in the susceptible population from European cohort studies, travel abroad was a significant risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis (pooled OR=2.153; $p<.0001$), as opposed to the Asian (pooled OR=1.281; $p=0.244$) and South American (pooled OR=0.734; $p=0.107$) studies where travel was not proven to be determinant of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population.

Table 2A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region for the mixed (n=12 ORs) and susceptible (n=10 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
South America	-0.153	0.103	12	[-0.355 – 0.049]	0.138
Susceptible					
Asia	0.248	0.213	3	[-0.169 – 0.666]	0.244
South America	-0.309	0.192	3	[-0.685 – 0.067]	0.107
Europe	0.767	0.162	4	[0.450 – 1.084]	<.0001

On average, mixed population people who travelled recently, either abroad (overall OR=0.692; 95% CI: 0.479 – 0.999) or within the country (overall OR=0.893; 95% CI: 0.694 – 1.148; Table 2B) were not at significant risk of becoming infected with toxoplasmosis than people who did not travel at all (Table 2B). However, travelling out of France, Norway, USA,

Canada, Saudi Arabia, Taiwan, Iran and Mexico increased the odds of infection of the susceptible population by an average of 1.636 (95% CI: 1.055 – 2.535; Table 2B). No data was found for children travelling abroad. Although the funnel plots visually suggested some evidence for bias on the meta-analyses conducted on the travel data partition (Figure 4), the formal test of study size effect failed to detect any publication bias either in the mixed (p=0.671) or in the susceptible population (p=0.675). No potentially-biased OR was removed from the mixed population meta-analysis after assessing influential observations by Cook's distance.

Table 2B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=12 ORs) and susceptible (n=10 ORs) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All Travel	-0.153	0.103	12	[-0.355 – 0.049]	0.138
(9 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	-0.368 ^a	0.187	4	[-0.735 – -0.001]	0.049
	Inside	-0.113 ^b	0.128	7	[-0.364 – 0.138]	0.376
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.2987	p=0.187		p=0.047	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0003			0.671
	Points removed	0				
Suscep	All Travel	0.492	0.223	10	[0.054 – 0.930]	0.028
(8 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad*	-0.012	0.163	6	[-0.333 – 0.308]	0.939
	Before 2000	0.772	0.245	4	[0.291 – 1.253]	0.001
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0158	QE(df=8)			
	s ² (residual)	0.6140	p=0.091			
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0004			0.675
	Points removed	0				

(*) Pooled OR for Travel Abroad after the year 2000

Figure 4. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of travel as a risk factor for toxoplasmosis in the mixed (left) and susceptible (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on host-specific factors revealed that, in most of the geographical regions, medical conditions significantly exacerbate the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed population, with pooled ORs varying from 1.663 ($p=0.026$) in Africa to 2.291 ($p=0.005$) in Europe, as well as in the susceptible population, with pooled ORs in the range of 1.566 (Asia; $p=0.008$) to 4.655 (South Europe; $p<.0001$). In South American children, the host-specific factors of suffering from mental retardation, having ascariasis or *Toxocara* infection increased the odds of acquiring toxoplasmosis by an average of 1.925 ($p=0.023$ in Table 3A).

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host-specific factors for toxoplasmosis by region for the mixed ($n=118$), children ($n=9$) and susceptible ($n=71$) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.509	0.229	13	[0.061 – 0.957]	0.026
Asia	0.655	0.136	43	[0.388 – 0.921]	<.0001
North America	0.354	0.300	9	[-0.232 – 0.941]	0.236
South America	0.556	0.136	49	[0.289 – 0.822]	<.0001
Europe	0.829	0.295	4	[0.251 – 1.408]	0.005
Children					
Asia	0.215	0.356	5	[-0.483 – 0.914]	0.545
South America	0.655	0.287	4	[0.091 – 1.219]	0.023
Susceptible					
Africa	0.535	0.198	19	[0.145 – 0.924]	0.007
Asia	0.449	0.171	25	[0.114 – 0.785]	0.008
South America	0.675	0.248	20	[0.189 – 1.161]	0.006
South Europe	1.538	0.402	7	[0.750 – 2.326]	<.0001

Table 3B. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=118), children (n=9) and susceptible population (n=71)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (37 stud)	All host-specific	0.589	0.084	118	[0.424 – 0.753]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Chronic	0.729 ^b	0.107	49	[0.519 – 0.938]	<.0001
	Hygiene	0.942 ^{ab}	0.420	5	[0.118 – 1.767]	0.025
	Other med	0.442 ^a	0.105	64	[0.235 – 0.648]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1527	QE(df=115)		QM(df=3)	
	s ² (residual)	0.6844	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.820
	Points removed	0				
Children (6 stud)	All host-specific	0.479	0.236	9	[0.016 – 0.942]	0.043
	Fixed effects					
	Hygiene	0.723 ^b	0.469	4	[-0.195 – 1.643]	0.122
	Other med	0.415 ^a	0.261	5	[-0.095 – 0.926]	0.111
	Before 2000					0.111
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2021	QE(df=7)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3112	p=0.001		p=0.085	
	Publication bias	0.0014	0.0004			0.001
	Points removed	0				
	Suscep (30 stud)	All host-specific	0.626	0.127	71	[0.376 – 0.875]
Fixed effects						
Antibiotic		0.225 ^a	0.354	4	[-0.468 – 0.919]	0.525
Chronic		0.350 ^a	0.205	13	[-0.050 – 0.751]	0.087
Hygiene		0.278 ^{ab}	0.498	2	[-0.697 – 1.254]	0.576
Other med		0.832 ^b	0.137	52	[0.564 – 1.100]	<.0001
Before 2000						0.868
Random effects						
s2u (Intercept)		0.1251	QE(df=67)		QM(df=4)	
s2 (residual)		0.6965	p<.0001		p<.0001	
Publication bias		0.0000	0.0005			0.935
Points removed	0					

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The general meta-analysis suggested that host-specific factors equally predisposed the susceptible population (overall OR=1.870; 95% CI: 1.456 – 2.400), the mixed population (overall OR=1.802; 95% CI: 1.528 – 2.123) and children (overall OR=1.614; 95% CI: 1.016 – 2.565) to acquiring toxoplasmosis (Table 3B). In the mixed population, having a chronic condition, such as schizophrenia, HIV, cancer, diabetes, Alzheimer, organ transplantation or memory impairment, predisposed people (overall OR=2.073; 95% CI: 1.680 – 2.555) to a greater extent than other medical conditions (overall OR=1.556; 95% CI: 1.265 – 1.912) such as lymphadenopathy, depression, use of corticosteroids, blood transfusion, liver disease, drug abuse or any surgery (Table 3B). Poor hygiene, such as poor hands hygiene and lack of protection when picking waste, seemingly was an important risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (overall OR=2.565; 95% CI: 1.125 – 5.853), although this pathway could not be accurately compared with the others since the extracted ORs in this subcategory were only five (Table 3B). For the children population, the data available on host-specific factors was limited as well. Nevertheless, at 15% significance, it is possible to state that poor hand hygiene is more important a risk factor for toxoplasmosis in children (overall OR=2.060; 95% CI: 0.823 – 5.171) than having other parasitic diseases such as ascariasis or *Toxocara* infection (overall OR=1.514; 95% CI: 0.909 – 2.524; Table 3B). In the susceptible population, people with toxoplasmosis were on average 2.298 times (95% CI:

1.758 – 3.004) more likely to suffer from medical conditions, such as hepatitis, lymphadenopathy, depression, blood transfusion, surgery history, intake of immunosuppressive drugs, high-dose prednisone or drug abuse, than non-ill people. At a significantly lower level of risk were the susceptible people suffering from chronic conditions such as hypertensive disorder, HIV, celiac disease, Alzheimer, diabetes, organ transplantation, memory transplantation and alcohol consumption (overall OR=1.419; 95% CI: 0.951 – 2.119; Table 3B). It is probable that, due to the few ORs available, the pooled association measures of recent use of antibiotics (overall OR=1.252; 95% CI: 0.626 – 2.507) and poor hygiene (overall OR=1.320; 95% CI: 0.498 – 3.504) did not reach statistical significance in the susceptible population (Table 3B). Publication bias was not evident either in the mixed population or in the susceptible population meta-analyses given both the lack of effect of study size on the measured ORs ($p=0.820$ and 0.935 , respectively), and the scattered distribution of observations within the funnel plots (Figure 5). Nonetheless, for host-specific factors in children, there was evidence of publication bias ($p<.0001$ in Table 3B), likely to arise from the fewer data points that could be retrieved in the literature for this population type (Figure 5).

Regarding the animal-related pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis, in the mixed population, animal contact was an important source of toxoplasmosis in developing countries from Africa (pooled OR=2.656; $p<.0001$), Asia (pooled OR=1.517; $p>.0001$) and South America (pooled OR=1.567; $p<.0001$), whereas it was of no significance in Western Europe (pooled OR=1.154; $p=0.409$) and Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.117; $p=0.628$). Nevertheless, in European countries from the Northern (pooled OR=1.761; $p=0.034$), Southern (pooled OR=3.000; $p=0.001$) and Western (pooled OR=1.401; $p=0.116$) regions, contact with animals played a significant role in the transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population, as well as in children from Southern Europe (pooled OR=1.723; $p=0.072$). Contact with animals posed a significant risk of toxoplasmosis also in the susceptible population from developing regions of Africa (pooled OR=2.044; $p<.0001$), Asia (pooled OR=1.426; $p<.0001$) and South America (pooled OR=1.478; $p<.0001$); and in children from Asia (pooled OR=1.619; $p=0.102$) and South America (pooled OR=1.902; $p<.0001$; Table 4A).

Taking together all the geographical regions, the risk of transmission of toxoplasmosis posed by any kind of contact with animals is equally high in the mixed (overall OR=1.711; 95% CI: 1.480 – 1.980), children (overall OR=1.586; 95% CI: 1.281 – 1.964) and susceptible population (overall OR=1.650; 95% CI: 1.492 – 1.828). Within the mixed population, occupational contact with animals, encompassing being a farmer, fishmonger, carrying out veterinarian duties or slaughtering animals (overall OR=2.010; 95% CI: 1.645 – 2.452), bore overall a significantly greater association with toxoplasmosis than having direct contact with cats and dogs (overall OR=1.685; 95% CI: 1.452 – 1.956). At a lower risk level laid the pathways of contact with farm animals – including leisure, contact with chickens, pork and home slaughtering (overall OR=1.433; 95% CI: 1.029 – 2.000) – and contact with wild animals, encompassing hunting activities, feral cats nearby and presence of rabbits, hamsters, rats and cockroaches at home (overall OR=1.471; 95% CI: 1.194 – 1.811; Table 4B). Likewise, in children, these two animal pathways, contact with farm animals (i.e., hens, pigs, cows; overall OR=1.243; 95% CI: 0.854 – 1.815) and wild animals (i.e., rabbit, hamster, rat, flies or cockroaches at home; overall OR=1.409; 95% CI: 1.063 – 1.870) bore the lowest risk of toxoplasmosis, while having cats was the most important pathway of infection in children (overall OR=1.634; 95% CI: 1.314 – 2.034; Table 4B).

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for toxoplasmosis by region in the mixed (n=235), children (n=82) and susceptible (n=230) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.977	0.158	28	[0.666 – 1.288]	<.0001
Asia	0.417	0.105	68	[0.212 – 0.622]	<.0001
North America	0.355	0.242	16	[-0.121 – 0.830]	0.144
North Europe	0.111	0.230	8	[-0.339 – 0.562]	0.628
South America	0.449	0.094	93	[0.264 – 0.633]	<.0001
West Europe	0.144	0.175	22	[-0.198 – 0.488]	0.409
Children					
Africa	0.018	0.233	13	[-0.439 – 0.476]	0.939
Asia	0.482	0.295	11	[-0.095 – 1.061]	0.102
Oceania	0.094	0.466	2	[-0.819 – 1.008]	0.839
South America	0.643	0.126	45	[0.396 – 0.889]	<.0001
South Europe	0.544	0.302	6	[-0.048 – 1.136]	0.072
West Europe	0.176	0.243	5	[-0.301 – 0.653]	0.471
Susceptible					
Africa	0.715	0.104	59	[0.510 – 0.919]	<.0001
Asia	0.355	0.098	50	[0.164 – 0.547]	<.0001
East Europe	0.264	0.330	5	[-0.383 – 0.911]	0.423
North Europe	0.566	0.266	26	[0.044 – 1.078]	0.034
South America	0.391	0.104	68	[0.187 – 0.595]	<.0001
South Europe	1.097	0.318	5	[0.474 – 1.721]	0.001
West Europe	0.337	0.214	17	[-0.083 – 0.757]	0.116

As occurred in the mixed population meta-analysis, in the susceptible population, occupational contact with animals (overall OR=1.777; 95% CI: 1.293 – 2.440) and contact with pets (overall OR=1.657; 95% CI: 1.456 – 1.870) were more relevant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis than contact with farm animals (overall OR=0.935; 95% CI: 0.668 – 1.309) and wild animals (overall OR=1.358; 95% CI: 0.947 – 1.948 in Table 4B). Furthermore, in the meta-analysis for each of the population types, there was no strong effect of study size on the published OR measures, as suggested by the formal test for publication bias (Table 4B) and the funnel plots (Figure 6).

Table 4B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=235), children (n=82) and susceptible (n=230) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (80 stud)	All animal	0.537	0.074	235	[0.392 – 0.683]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.360 ^{ab}	0.169	9	[0.029 – 0.691]	0.033
	Occupational	0.698 ^c	0.101	67	[0.498 – 0.897]	<.0001
	Pets	0.522 ^b	0.076	145	[0.373 – 0.671]	<.0001
	Wild	0.386 ^a	0.106	14	[0.177 – 0.594]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.110	0.047		[-0.203 – -0.017]	0.020
	Before 2000					0.972
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2545	QE(df=230)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5449	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.095
Points removed	0					
Children (15 stud)	All animal	0.461	0.109	82	[0.248 – 0.675]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.218 ^a	0.192	5	[-0.158 – 0.596]	0.255
	Pets	0.491 ^b	0.111	72	[0.273 – 0.710]	<.0001
	Wild	0.343 ^a	0.144	5	[0.061 – 0.626]	0.017
	Before 2000					0.951
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1306	QE(df=79)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3594	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.303
	Points removed	0				
	Suscep (84 stud)	All animal	0.501	0.051	230	[0.400 – 0.603]
Fixed effects						
Farm		-0.067 ^a	0.172	11	[-0.403 – 0.269]	0.695
Occupational		0.575 ^{ab}	0.162	10	[0.257 – 0.892]	<.0001
Pets		0.505 ^b	0.064	202	[0.376 – 0.626]	<.0001
Wild		0.306 ^{ab}	0.184	7	[-0.054 – 0.667]	0.095
Before 2000						0.802
Random effects						

s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2028	QE(df=226)	QM(df=4)
s^2 (residual)	0.5675	p<.0001	p<.0001
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001	0.089
Points removed	0		

Figure 6. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of animal contact pathways as risk factors for toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

With respect to the environmental pathways of exposure in the mixed population, the pooled risk measures were significantly associated with toxoplasmosis in all geographical regions (overall ORs ranging from 1.352 in North America to 3.034 in Africa), with the only exception being Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.038; p=0.947; Table 5A). In children, except for Africa, the environmental routes were strongly associated with toxoplasmosis in all of the geographical regions: Asia (pooled OR=1.559; p<.0001), North America (pooled OR=5.012; p<.0001), South America (pooled OR=1.344; p<.0001) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.733; p=0.001) (Table 5A). Likewise, the multiple environmental routes were significant in the transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population from all the world's regions, with pooled ORs ranging from 1.474 in South America to 1.990 in Eastern Europe (Table 5A). For the subsequent general meta-analysis by subcategory, data from the African region were removed in the mixed population and children, for presenting the highest and the lowest pooled OR, respectively.

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by region in the mixed (n=242), children (n=56) and susceptible (n=210) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	1.110	0.171	27	[0.775 – 1.446]	<.0001
Asia	0.380	0.096	75	[0.192 – 0.567]	<.0001
East Europe	0.361	0.174	11	[0.021 – 0.702]	0.037
North America	0.302	0.193	13	[-0.076 – 0.679]	0.118
North Europe	0.038	0.571	3	[-1.080 – 1.156]	0.947
South America	0.522	0.095	92	[0.337 – 0.708]	<.0001
West Europe	0.517	0.194	21	[0.137 – 0.898]	0.008
Children					
Africa	-0.223	0.090	6	[-0.400 – -0.046]	0.013
Asia	0.444	0.068	12	[0.309 – 0.578]	<.0001
North America	1.612	0.300	2	[1.023 – 2.200]	<.0001
South America	0.296	0.059	34	[0.179 – 0.412]	<.0001
West Europe	0.550	0.170	2	[0.217 – 0.883]	0.001
Susceptible					
Africa	0.389	0.116	48	[0.162 – 0.617]	0.001
Asia	0.447	0.116	51	[0.221 – 0.674]	<.0001
East Europe	0.688	0.262	5	[0.175 – 1.201]	0.008
North Europe	0.407	0.288	14	[-0.158 – 0.972]	0.158
South America	0.388	0.112	74	[0.168 – 0.607]	0.001
West Europe	0.649	0.213	18	[0.232 – 1.067]	0.002

The multiple environmental pathways were equally important sources of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (overall OR=1.540; 95% CI: 1.392 – 1.704), children (overall OR=1.701; 95% CI: 1.332 – 2.175) and susceptible population (overall OR=1.564; 95% CI: 1.385 – 1.765; Table 5B). Recreational water, including swimming in sea, ponds, lake and river, did not appear to be a significant route of transmission of toxoplasmosis, either in the mixed population (overall OR=1.327; 95% CI: 0.681 – 2.588) or in the susceptible population (overall OR=0.738; 95% CI: 0.529 – 1.029). In the mixed population, contact with soil (i.e., playground) bore the greatest risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis among the different environmental pathways: people with toxoplasmosis infection were, on average, 1.935 times (95% CI: 1.490 – 2.512) more likely to have had contact with soil through gardening or soil-related jobs than non-ill people. A significantly lower association with toxoplasmosis was found for the exposures related to drinking water (overall OR=1.680; 95% CI: 1.283 – 2.199) and farm environment (overall OR=1.637; 95% CI: 1.252 – 2.138 in Table 5B). While the drinking water exposure encompassed drinking untreated water, well water, private source

water, surface water, unfiltered water and unboiled water in deprived regions; the farm environment exposure included living on a farm, rural residence or agriculture occupation. Due to the large variability in the few ORs encountered for the waste water exposure, this category was not found to differ statistically from the others (overall OR=1.556; 95% CI: 0.850 – 2.843), and hence it could not be ranked in importance among the environmental sources. In both, the children and susceptible population, living on a farm was the most important environmental determinant of toxoplasmosis, with pooled ORs of 2.018 (95% CI: 1.699 – 2.394) and 1.752 (95% CI: 1.426 – 2.153). At an equally lower risk of toxoplasmosis in children laid the pathways of drink water (overall OR=1.380; 95% CI: 1.200 – 1.590) – which grouped untreated water, well/spring/river water, and non-chlorinated/unboiled water – and exposure to waste water (overall OR=1.565; 95% CI: 1.339 – 1.828), which encompassed garbage accumulation at home, and absence of sewage system or open sewage in deprived regions. Playground – made up of contact with soil, playing in soil and contact with garden – bore the lowest risk of acquiring *Toxoplasma gondii* in children at an overall OR of 1.125 (95% CI: 0.972 – 1.302 in Table 5B). On meta-analysis, the susceptible population appeared equally likely to acquiring toxoplasmosis when exposed to human waste (including no access to basic sanitation, untreated sewage and no public collection of garbage; overall OR=1.883; 95% CI: 1.179 – 3.007), when drinking untreated water (i.e., unboiled/unfiltered tap water, well/river/rain water and storage tank water; overall OR=1.396; 95% CI: 1.208 – 1.613) or when exposed to soil (overall OR=1.490; 95% CI: 1.334 – 1.664; Table 5B). In addition, although the OR measures appeared to be well distributed within the funnel plots (Figure 7), the OR measures were found to depend upon study size in the meta-analyses of the mixed (p=0.048) and the susceptible population (p=0.055).

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=215), children (n=50) and susceptible (n=210) population – African countries removed from the mixed and children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All environment	0.432	0.052	215	[0.331 – 0.533]	<.0001
(71 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Drink water	0.519 ^a	0.138	71	[0.249 – 0.788]	<.0001
	Farm	0.493 ^a	0.137	65	[0.225 – 0.760]	<.0001
	Playground*	0.660 ^b	0.133	69	[0.399 – 0.921]	<.0001
	Rec water	0.283 ^a	0.341	4	[-0.384 – 0.951]	0.409
	Waste water	0.442 ^{ab}	0.308	6	[-0.162 – 1.045]	0.141
	Before 2000					0.914
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1520	QE(df=210)		QM(df=5)	
	s ² (residual)	0.4366	p<.0001		p=.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0000			0.048
	Points removed	0				

Children	All environment	0.531	0.125	50	[0.287 – 0.7775]	<.0001
(9 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Drink water	0.322 ^b	0.072	23	[0.182 – 0.464]	<.0001
	Farm	0.702 ^c	0.087	7	[0.530 – 0.873]	<.0001
	Playground*	0.118 ^a	0.074	15	[-0.028 – 0.264]	0.114
	Waste water	0.448 ^b	0.079	5	[0.292 – 0.603]	<.0001
	Before 2000	0.168	0.107		[-0.042 – 0.378]	0.116
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=45)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	0.1919	p=0.051		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	0.0001	0.0001			0.474
	Points removed	0				
Suscep	All environment	0.447	0.062	210	[0.326 – 0.568]	<.0001
(75 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Drink water	0.334 ^b	0.074	55	[0.189 – 0.478]	<.0001
	Farm	0.561 ^c	0.105	57	[0.355 – 0.767]	<.0001
	Playground*	0.399 ^b	0.056	84	[0.288 – 0.509]	<.0001
	Recreat water	-0.304 ^a	0.170	3	[-0.636 – 0.029]	0.074
	Waste water	0.633 ^{bc}	0.239	11	[0.165 – 1.101]	0.008
	Before 2000					0.340
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2084	QE(df=205)		QM(df=5)	
	s ² (residual)	0.4941	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.055
	Points removed	0				

(*) Contact with garden and exposure to soil

Since only three primary studies were found to report outcomes on the person-to-person contagion, results from the meta-analysis on this partition should be interpreted cautiously. Despite the small size of this data partition, there was no evidence for publication bias (p=0.158 in Table 6 and Figure 8). On meta-analysis, susceptible people who had contact with any toxoplasmosis case presented 2.801 times (95% CI: 0.918 – 8.551) greater risk of acquiring the disease than those who did not. However, the risk of person-to-person contagion in the mixed population (overall OR=1.649; 95% CI: 0.574 – 4.730) could not be proven to be of significance (Table 6).

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 6. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of toxoplasmosis in the combined mixed (n=3) and susceptible (n=2) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Both	Fixed effects					
(3 stud)	Mixed	0.500 ^a	0.538	3	[-0.555 – 1.554]	0.353
	Susceptible	1.030 ^a	0.569	2	[-0.086 – 2.146]	0.070
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.5018	QE(df=3)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.1532	p=0.006		p=0.195	
	Publication bias	0.0178	0.0126			0.158
	Points removed	0				

Figure 8. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of toxoplasmosis in the combined mixed and susceptible population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis by geographical region demonstrated that food was an important vehicle of transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii* in both the mixed and susceptible population (Table 7A). Toxoplasmosis was significantly associated with food ingestion in the mixed populations from Africa (pooled OR=2.280; $p < .0001$), Asia (pooled OR=1.704; $p < .0001$), Eastern Europe (pooled OR=1.846; $p = 0.007$), North America (pooled OR=2.349; $p = 0.001$), South America (pooled OR=1.542; $p < .0001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.941; $p < .0001$). A similar range of overall risk was observed in the susceptible populations from Africa (pooled OR=1.728; $p < .0001$), Asia (pooled OR=1.525; $p < .0001$), Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.655; $p = 0.063$), South America (pooled OR=1.442; $p = 0.001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=2.143; $p < .0001$). Thus, while in most of the geographical regions, food was demonstrated to be an important source of toxoplasmosis, only in the cohort studies conducted on the mixed population of Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.362; $p = 0.479$) and on the susceptible population from Eastern Europe (pooled OR=1.241; $p = 0.611$), food was not found to be associated with toxoplasmosis. Interestingly, in children from developing regions of Africa (pooled OR=0.959; $p = 0.889$) and South America (pooled OR=1.275; $p = 0.205$), food did not appear to be an important vehicle for the transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii* (Table 7A). No geographical region was removed for the subsequent meta-analysis by food subcategory.

The general meta-analysis on food pathways showed that, as a whole, the susceptible population were as likely to become infected with *Toxoplasma gondii* through food consumption (overall OR=1.728; 95% CI: 1.546 – 1.931) than the mixed population (overall OR=1.605; 95% CI: 1.433 – 1.799), while children were at a lower level of predisposition (overall OR=1.256; 95% CI: 0.967 – 1.631 in Table 7B). On meta-analysis, the mixed population with toxoplasmosis infection were more likely to have consumed meat (including beef, chicken, mutton, goat, pork, boar, pigeon, duck, venison, squirrel, sheep, duck, rabbit, horse, turkey, BBQ meat, mince meat and processed/cured meat; overall OR=1.752; 95% CI: 1.539 – 1.994), produce (including fresh vegetables and fruits, mostly raw or unwashed; overall OR=1.782; 95% CI: 1.487 – 2.138) or seafood (made up of raw fish, molluscs, oysters, clams and shellfish; overall OR=1.789; 95% CI: 1.019 – 3.139) than the controls (Table 7B). A lower association with toxoplasmosis in the mixed population was found for

the food subcategories of dairy (encompassing raw milk, soft cheese, home-made sour cream and any dairy; overall OR=1.314; 95% CI: 1.015 – 1.700) and composite foods (including luncheon, dishes eaten out, kibbeh, BBQ and non-vegeterian dishes; overall OR=1.377; 95% CI: 0.876 – 2.162).

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=406), children (n=35) and susceptibility (n=430) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.824	0.165	34	[0.500 – 1.147]	<.0001
Asia	0.533	0.097	92	[0.343 – 0.722]	<.0001
East Europe	0.613	0.228	11	[0.165 – 1.060]	0.007
North America	0.854	0.254	10	[0.357 – 1.351]	0.001
North Europe	0.309	0.436	10	[-0.545 – 1.163]	0.479
South America	0.433	0.080	216	[0.276 – 0.591]	<.0001
West Europe	0.663	0.183	33	[0.304 – 1.022]	<.0001
Children					
Africa	-0.042	0.300	5	[-0.629 – 0.545]	0.889
South America	0.243	0.191	30	[-0.132 – 0.618]	0.205
Susceptible					
Africa	0.547	0.112	58	[0.328 – 0.766]	<.0001
Asia	0.422	0.101	81	[0.225 – 0.619]	<.0001
East Europe	0.216	0.425	10	[-0.617 – 1.050]	0.611
North Europe	0.504	0.271	83	[-0.026 – 1.035]	0.063
South America	0.366	0.110	157	[0.150 – 0.582]	0.001
West Europe	0.762	0.211	41	[0.348 – 1.175]	<.0001

Eating raw eggs was not found to be a source of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (overall OR=1.165; 95% CI: 0.678 – 2.000; Table 7B). In the children population, meats encompassing beef, pork, duck, chicken, turkey, deer, rabbit, lamb, cured meats and non-specific meats (overall OR=1.461; 95% CI: 1.178 – 1.811) constituted a stronger determinant of toxoplasmosis infection than dairy, represented by milk and powdered milk (overall OR=1.251; 95% CI: 0.919 – 1.706). There was no evidence on meta-analysis that produce was an important vehicle of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children (overall OR=0.904; 95% CI: 0.756 – 1.080). As in the mixed population, meat was the most important food source of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population (overall OR=1.740; 95% CI: 1.520 – 1.992), followed by raw or undercooked eggs (overall OR=1.454; 95% CI: 0.951 – 2.221), produce (unwashed or raw fruits and vegetables; overall OR=1.406; 95% CI: 1.156 – 1.709) and dairy (raw milk, homemade cheese, goat milk, fresh cheese and powder milk; overall OR=1.262; 95% CI: 0.995 – 1.602).

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=404), children (n=34) and susceptible (n=429) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All foods	0.547	0.056	404	[0.436 – 0.658]	<.0001
(73 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.320 ^{ab}	0.230	13	[-0.132 – 0.771]	0.165
	Dairy	0.273 ^a	0.131	30	[0.015 – 0.531]	0.038
	Eggs*	0.153 ^a	0.276	6	[-0.388 – 0.693]	0.580
	Meat	0.561 ^b	0.066	275	[0.431 – 0.690]	<.0001
	Produce	0.578 ^b	0.093	68	[0.397 – 0.760]	<.0001
	Seafood	0.582 ^b	0.287	12	[0.019 – 1.144]	0.043
	Before 2000					0.472
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1849	QE(df=398)		QM(df=6)	
	s ² (residual)	0.6363	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.048
	Points removed	0				
Children	All foods	0.228	0.133	34	[-0.033 – 0.489]	0.087
(8 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dairy	0.224 ^b	0.158	5	[-0.084 – 0.534]	0.154
	Meat	0.379 ^b	0.110	20	[0.164 – 0.594]	0.001
	Produce	-0.101 ^a	0.091	9	[-0.279 – 0.077]	0.265
	Before 2000	-0.427	0.182		[-0.783 – -0.071]	0.018
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=30)		QM(df=3)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3965	p=0.587		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	-0.0008	0.0003			0.014
	Points removed	1				
Suscep	All foods	0.473	0.058	429	[0.360 – 0.587]	<.0001
(80 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beverages**	0.319 ^{abc}	0.523	3	[-0.706 – 1.345]	0.542
	Composite	0.268 ^a	0.208	12	[-0.140 – 0.676]	0.198
	Dairy	0.233 ^a	0.121	45	[-0.005 – 0.471]	0.055
	Eggs*	0.374 ^{ab}	0.216	10	[-0.050 – 0.798]	0.083
	Meat	0.554 ^c	0.069	293	[0.419 – 0.689]	<.0001
	Produce	0.341 ^b	0.100	66	[0.145 – 0.536]	0.001

Before 2000			0.336
Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2665	QE(df=423)	QM(df=6)
s^2 (residual)	0.5868	p<.0001	p<.0001
Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0001	0.001
Points removed	0		

(*) Eggs subcategory is formed of the Eggs class only
 (**) Ice made of water and fruits in Brazil

In the susceptible population, neither ice made of water and fruits (viz, beverages; overall OR=1.375; p=0.542) nor composite foods (overall OR=1.307; p=0.198) were found to be determinant of toxoplasmosis. After Cook's distance assessment, only one potentially-biased OR popped up as influential points in the children meta-analysis, and hence, it was removed (Table 7B). Despite the extensive data extracted from the literature, the formal tests for publication bias indicated a strong effect of study size on the measured ORs in the meta-analyses for the mixed population (p=0.048), the children population (p=0.014) and the susceptible population (p=0.001 in Table 7B). Nonetheless, the residuals within the respective funnel plots appeared well distributed (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on meat pathways of transmission showed that in the mixed population, there was a strong association between consumption of meat and toxoplasmosis in most of the geographical regions, except for Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.132; p=0.780). Overall ORs were all significant and ranged between 1.624 in Latin American countries to 2.372 in North America (Table 8A). Likewise, in the susceptible population, meat was a significant source of *Toxoplasma gondii* in countries from Africa (pooled OR=1.958; p<.0001), Asia (pooled OR=1.726; p<.0001), South America (pooled OR=1.484; p=0.001) and Western Europe (pooled OR=2.519; p>.0001), although it was a minor source in Northern (pooled OR=1.709; p=0.127) and Eastern Europe (pooled OR=1.288; p=0.634). In children from Africa and Latin America, however, there was no association between meat consumption and toxoplasmosis (pooled OR=1.181 and 1.366; p=0.672 and 0.191, respectively, in Table 8A). For the general meta-analysis by meat class (Table 8B), no geographical region was removed.

Table 8A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=275), children (n=20) and susceptible (n=293) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.615	0.192	16	[0.238 – 0.993]	0.001
Asia	0.538	0.101	54	[0.340 – 0.736]	<.0001
East Europe	0.580	0.227	7	[0.135 – 1.025]	0.011
North America	0.864	0.252	8	[0.369 – 1.358]	0.001
North Europe	0.124	0.442	7	[-0.742 – 0.989]	0.780
South America	0.485	0.085	164	[0.318 – 0.650]	<.0001
West Europe	0.627	0.203	19	[0.230 – 1.024]	0.002
Children					
Africa	0.166	0.391	2	[-0.601 – 0.932]	0.672
South America	0.312	0.239	18	[-0.156 – 0.779]	0.191
Susceptible					
Africa	0.672	0.146	38	[0.385 – 0.958]	<.0001
Asia	0.546	0.137	44	[0.278 – 0.814]	<.0001
East Europe	0.253	0.532	6	[-0.789 – 1.296]	0.634
North Europe	0.536	0.351	71	[-0.153 – 1.225]	0.127
South America	0.395	0.146	99	[0.109 – 0.681]	0.001
West Europe	0.924	0.280	35	[0.374 – 1.474]	<.0001

Table 8B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=275), children (n=20) and susceptible (n=293) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (68 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beef	0.390 ^b	0.156	23	[0.085 – 0.695]	0.012
	Other red meat	0.592 ^c	0.123	44	[0.350 – 0.834]	<.0001
	Others	0.547 ^{bc}	0.066	144	[0.417 – 0.676]	<.0001
	Pork	0.608 ^c	0.168	23	[0.280 – 0.937]	<.0001
	Poultry	0.369 ^b	0.174	18	[0.028 – 0.710]	0.034
	Proc meat	0.215 ^a	0.147	23	[-0.072 – 0.502]	0.143
	Before 2000					0.800
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1195	QE(df=269)		QM(df=6)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.6704	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.021
Points removed	0					
Children (7 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Red meats*	0.243 ^b	0.409	4	[-0.559 – 1.046]	0.552
	Others	0.336 ^b	0.202	10	[-0.060 – 0.731]	0.096
	Poultry	-0.316 ^a	0.494	3	[-1.284 – 0.652]	0.522
	Proc meat**	0.785 ^c	0.376	3	[0.294 – 1.767]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.444
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3425	QE(df=16)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4623	p=0.428		p=0.030	
	Publication bias	-0.0013	0.0007			0.064
	Points removed	0				
	Suscep (77 stud)	Fixed effects				
Beef		0.746 ^c	0.194	31	[0.368 – 1.129]	<.0001
Other red meat		0.622 ^b	0.180	43	[0.270 – 0.974]	0.001
Others		0.564 ^{ab}	0.082	137	[0.403 – 0.725]	<.0001
Pork		0.492 ^a	0.223	28	[0.055 – 0.929]	0.027
Poultry		0.468 ^a	0.201	23	[0.074 – 0.862]	0.020
Proc meat		0.463 ^a	0.206	31	[0.031 – 0.840]	0.035
Before 2000						0.772

Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3331	QE(df=287)	QM(df=6)
s^2 (residual)	0.7242	p<.0001	p<.0001
Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0001	0.001
Points removed	0		

(*) Including beef

(**) Comprises rare pork (Panama) and cured meat (Brazil)

On average, ill people from the mixed population were more likely to have consumed pork (including undercooked pork; overall OR=1.837; 95% CI: 1.323 – 2.552), red meats other than beef (including sheep, goat, venison, horse, mutton and boar meat; overall OR=1.808; 95% CI: 1.419 – 2.303) or other meats (non-specific meat, offal, rabbit, pigeon, squirrel, opossum, iguana, armadillo, quail, bear, tigrillo and turtle; overall OR=1.728; 95% CI: 1.517 – 1.966) than people without toxoplasmosis (Table 8B). At a slightly lower level of mean risk laid the pathways of beef (encompassing also raw/undercooked beef and dried beef; overall OR=1.477; 1.088 – 2.003) and poultry meat (chicken, turkey and duck; overall OR=1.446; 95% CI: 1.028 – 2.033). In the mixed population, processed meats including ham, salami, raw dried meat, chorizo, homemade sausages and cured meats bore the lowest risk of toxoplasmosis. In children, pork and processed meats (data from studies from Brazil and Panama) presented overall the highest association with toxoplasmosis (overall OR=2.192; 95% CI: 1.341 – 5.853), followed by the group of other meats, including non-specific undercooked/raw meat, iguana, deer and rabbit (overall OR=1.399; 95% CI: 0.941 – 2.077). In children, the consumption of red meats, including beef (overall OR=1.275; 95% CI: 0.572 – 2.846) and poultry (overall OR=0.729; 95% CI: 0.277 – 1.919) were not proven to be important sources of toxoplasmosis, likely to arise from the very few observations retrieved for these food classes (Table 8B). In the susceptible population, consuming rare/undercooked beef, beef mince or beef tongue conveyed the highest risk of toxoplasmosis (overall OR=2.109; 95% CI: 1.445 – 3.093), followed by other red meats, such as sheep, venison, horse, boar, deer and mutton (overall OR=1.863; 95% CI: 1.310 – 2.648) and other meats, such as non-classified meats, pigeon, rabbit, iguana, armadillo, pigeon, skunk, squirrel and game meat (overall OR=1.757; 95% CI: 1.496 – 2.065). Although still significant, pork (encompassing raw/cured pork, undercooked pork, mince pork; overall OR=1.636; 95% CI: 1.057 – 2.532), poultry (overall OR=1.597; 95% CI: 1.077 – 2.368) and processed meats (namely, sausages, chorizo, ham, salami, bacon, dry meat, homemade sausage and delicatessen meat; overall OR=1.589; 95% CI: 1.031 – 2.316) presented a lower level of association with toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population. It is worth mentioning that within each meat class – except for poultry meat, the association with toxoplasmosis was stronger in the susceptible population than in the mixed population, as denoted by the lower p-values of the former (Table 8B). As occurred in the all-foods data partition, the formal tests for publication bias in the meat meta-analyses also indicated a strong effect of study size on the measured ORs for the mixed population (p=0.021), the children population (p=0.064) and the susceptible population (p=0.001 in Table 8B). Nonetheless, the residuals within the respective funnel plots appeared well distributed (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left) children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analyses by geographical region on the dairy pathways of exposure revealed that produce was an important vehicle for the transmission of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population from Western Europe (pooled OR=1.378; $p=0.111$) and Africa (pooled OR=1.690; $p=0.010$) and in the susceptible population from Asia (pooled OR=1.572; $p=0.043$). In the European population, the consumption of raw dairy products was not a risk factor of toxoplasmosis (overall OR=0.957; $p=0.887$), probably because European pregnant women receive more pre-natal care advice on safe foods and practices for healthy gestation (Table 9A). Taking all geographical regions together (Table 9B), in both the mixed and susceptible population, raw milk was more associated with toxoplasmosis (overall OR=1.273; 95% CI: 1.030 – 1.576; and overall OR=1.339; 95% CI: 1.073 – 1.674, respectively) than dairy products (overall OR=1.174; 95% CI: 0.763 – 1.811; and overall OR=0.983; 95% CI: 0.611 – 1.582, respectively). Nevertheless, milk was not a significant vehicle of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children (overall OR=1.241; $p=0.360$), probably because the exposure evaluated was “milk” and not “raw milk” as took place in the mixed and susceptible population. As implied by both funnel plots (Figure 11) and the test of effect of study size on ORs (Table 9B), there was evidence of publication bias only for the children’s dairy pathway ($p=0.012$).

Table 9A. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=28), children (n=5) and susceptible (n=45) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.525	0.205	6	[0.123 – 0.927]	0.010
South America	0.082	0.123	12	[-0.159 – 0.323]	0.506
West Europe	0.321	0.202	10	[-0.074 – 0.718]	0.111
Children					
South America	0.187	0.192	5	[-0.189 – 0.564]	0.330
Susceptible					
Africa	0.123	0.297	7	[-0.459 – 0.706]	0.678
Asia	0.4527	0.225	13	[0.015 – 0.899]	0.043
South America	0.214	0.204	19	[-0.185 – 0.613]	0.294
Europe	-0.044	0.307	6	[-0.645 – 0.558]	0.887

Figure 11. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 9B. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=28), children (n=4) and susceptible (n=44) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (19 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Raw milk	0.242 ^b	0.108	23	[0.030 – 0.455]	0.025
	Milk prods	0.161 ^a	0.220	5	[-0.271 – 0.594]	0.465
	Before 2000					0.545
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0454	QE(df=26)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3693	p=0.003		p=0.062	
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0001			0.769
	Points removed	0				
	Children (1 stud)	Fixed effects				
Milk		0.216	0.236	4	[-0.246 – 0.678]	0.360
Before 2000						ND
Random effects						
s ² _u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=3)			
s ² (residual)		0.3327	p=0.080			
Publication bias		-0.0028	0.0011			0.012
Points removed		0				
Suscep (28 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Cheese	-0.017 ^a	0.243	6	[-0.493 – 0.459]	0.944
	Raw milk	0.292 ^b	0.113	38	[0.070 – 0.515]	0.010
	Before 2000					0.366
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2450	QE(df=42)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.3603	p<.0001		p=0.036	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0004			0.802
	Points removed	0				

The meta-analysis on produce demonstrated that, as a whole, raw vegetables and fruits represented major pathways for acquiring *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in the different geographical regions (Table 10A): the African mixed population (pooled OR=2.208; p<.0001), the Asian mixed (pooled OR=1.784; p<.0001) and susceptible (pooled OR=1.344; p=0.007) population, the European mixed (pooled OR=4.043; p<.0001) and susceptible (pooled OR=1.929; p<.0001) population, and the South American mixed (pooled OR=1.398;

p=0.009) and susceptible (pooled OR=1.328; p=0.005) population. Interestingly, on meta-analysis, consumption of raw vegetables was not an important pathway of transmission of toxoplasmosis in African (pooled OR=0.927) and South American (pooled OR=0.768) children.

Table 10A. Meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=68), children (n=9) and susceptible (n=66) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Africa	0.792	0.201	11	[0.397 – 1.186]	<.0001
Asia	0.579	0.150	22	[0.285 – 0.873]	<.0001
Europe	1.397	0.305	6	[0.800 – 1.994]	<.0001
South America	0.335	0.127	29	[0.086 – 0.585]	0.009
Children					
Africa	-0.076	0.111	3	[-0.294 – 0.142]	0.495
South America	-0.264	0.149	6	[-0.555 – 0.028]	<.0001
Susceptible					
Africa	0.132	0.140	12	[-0.143 – 0.407]	0.347
Asia	0.296	0.110	16	[0.081 – 0.511]	0.007
Europe	0.657	0.160	11	[0.343 – 0.972]	<.0001
South America	0.284	0.101	27	[0.085 – 0.482]	0.005

On average, people from the mixed population who consumed raw/unwashed vegetables presented 1.811 times (95% CI: 1.481 – 2.217; Table 10B) greater odds of becoming infected with toxoplasmosis than those who did not. Such level of risk was significantly higher than that of people from the mixed population exposed through the ingestion of unwashed fruits, which presented a lower overall OR at 1.369 (95% CI: 0.837 – 2.239), not reaching statistical significance. In the susceptible population, both sources, unwashed/raw vegetables (overall OR=1.297; 95% CI: 1.131 – 1.487) and unwashed fruits (overall OR=1.534; 95% CI: 1.059 – 2.221) were significantly associated with toxoplasmosis, at a similar level of risk. On meta-analysis, the consumption of raw vegetables did not bear any risk for the transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii* in African and South American children (overall OR=0.867; 95% CI: 0.728 – 1.033). No evidence for publication bias was found in the produce pathways meta-analyses, as implied by the non-significant p-values compiled in Table 10A, and the homogeneous spread of OR measures within the funnel plots of Figure 12.

Table 10B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=68), children (n=9) and susceptible (n=66) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed (42 stud)	Fixed effects						
	Unwashed fruits	0.314 ^a	0.251	8	[-0.178 – 0.806]	0.211	
	Vegetables*	0.594 ^b	0.194	60	[0.393 – 0.796]	<.0001	
	Before 2000					0.321	
	Random effects						
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1793	QE(df=66)		QM(df=2)		
	s ² (residual)	0.5170	p<.0001		p<.0001		
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0002			0.466	
	Points removed	0					
	Children (5 stud)	Fixed effects					
Raw vegs		-0.143	0.0891	9	[-0.318 – 0.032]	0.108	
Before 2000						0.194	
Random effects							
s ² _u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=9)				
s ² (residual)		0.2623	p=0.026				
Publication bias		-0.0004	0.0013			0.736	
Points removed		0					
Suscep (38 stud)		Fixed effects					
		Unwashed fruits	0.428 ^a	0.189	9	[0.057 – 0.798]	0.024
	Vegetables*	0.260 ^a	0.070	57	[0.123 – 0.397]	<.0001	
	Before 2000	0.344	0.193		[-0.034 – 0.722]	0.075	
	Random effects						
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0706	QE(df=63)		QM(df=2)		
	s ² (residual)	0.1812	p<.0001		p=0.901		
	Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.961	
	Points removed	0					

(*) Mostly made up of unwashed or raw vegetables

Figure 12. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (top left), children (top right) and susceptible (bottom) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

A limited amount of data was available on the association of toxoplasmosis with seafood, and originated mostly from Asian primary studies (Table 11A). In the Asian mixed population, people who ingested any seafood presented, on average, 1.469 times greater probability ($p=0.034$) of acquiring toxoplasmosis than those who did not. However, when meta-analysing by seafood class, it was possible to discern that while fish did not reach significance as determinant of disease (overall OR=1.037; 95% CI: 0.762 – 1.411), the consumption of raw molluscs conveyed a high risk of toxoplasmosis infection in the Asian countries (overall OR=1.950; 95% CI: 1.433 – 2.654 in Table 11B).

Table 11A. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption related pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region* in the mixed population (n=10)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.385	0.182	10	[0.029 – 0.742]	0.034

(*) Other ORs originate from North America (1 OR), South America (1 OR) and Western Europe (1 OR) and were excluded for this analysis

Table 11B. Meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the combined mixed (n=12) and susceptible (n=1) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
(5 stud)	Fish	0.036 ^a	0.157	4	[-0.272 – 0.344]	0.820
	Raw molluscs	0.668 ^b	0.157	9	[0.360 – 0.976]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.4400	QE(df=11)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2561	p=0.185		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0002			0.088
	Points removed	0				

In the seafood data partition, although the OR residuals were homogeneously distributed within the funnel plot (Figure 13), the formal test of study size effect revealed that it is likely that some results failing to quantify a significant association between seafood consumption and toxoplasmosis may have remained unpublished (p=0.088 in Table 11).

Figure 13. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of seafood consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the combined mixed and susceptible population

Composite foods, mostly comprising food prepared outside the home, constituted another source of toxoplasmosis in the mixed (pooled OR=7.830; p<.0001) and susceptible (pooled OR=1.707; p<.0001) population from Asia (Table 12A). By contrary, in South America, there was no evidence that multi-ingredient foods or dishes eaten out could be important vehicles of transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii* either in the mixed (pooled OR=0.944; p=0.854) or in the susceptible population (pooled OR=0.904; p=0.518 in Table 12B).

Table 12A. Meta-analyses of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis by geographical region in the mixed (n=12) and susceptible (n=12) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	2.058	0.561	3	[0.959 – 3.157]	<.0001
South America	-0.057	0.311	9	[-0.666 – 0.552]	0.854
Susceptible					
Asia	0.535	0.136	4	[0.268 – 0.801]	<.0001
East Europe	0.216	0.187	2	[-0.152 – 0.584]	0.250
South America	-0.101	0.156	6	[-0.406 – 0.205]	0.518

Table 12B. Meta-analyses of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (n=12) and susceptible (n=12) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed						
(9 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dishes	-0.068	0.298	12	[-0.652 – 0.515]	0.818
	Before 2000					0.321
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3412	QE(df=11)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.5235	p=0.001			
	Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0005			0.182
Points removed	0					
Suscep						
(10 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dishes	0.213 ^a	0.139	10	[-0.060 – 0.486]	0.127
	RTE	0.612 ^a	0.378	2	[-0.130 – 1.354]	0.106
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0606	QE(df=10)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1681	p=0.112		p=0.084	
Publication bias	0.0003	0.0008			0.745	
Points removed	0					

In the category of composite foods, there was virtually no data available from European cohort studies (Table 12A). The general meta-analysis by food class showed that the susceptible population were more vulnerable to acquire toxoplasmosis through consumption of multi-ingredient foods or dishes prepared outside the home (overall OR=0.934; 95% CI: 0.521 – 1.674) than were the mixed population (overall OR=1.237; 95% CI: 0.942 – 1.625 in Table 12B). The level of risk associated to RTE deli foods could not be accurately synthesised, since only two ORs were available for this meta-analysis. Thus, the pooled OR of 1.844 (95% CI: 0.878 – 3.873) is by no means generalisable. In this meta-analysis, the observations were well dispersed within the funnel plot, therefore clueing the unlikely presence of publication bias (Figure 14), which was also corroborated by the non-significant effect of study size on the OR measures ($p=0.182$ and $p=0.745$; Table 12B).

Figure 14. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of composite food consumption pathways for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed (left) and susceptible (right) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

3.8.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of toxoplasmosis due to consumption of raw/rare meats, unwashed vegetables/fruits and contact with cats

A common denominator of the cohort studies this meta-analysis based upon was the examination of three risk factors: consumption of raw/rare meat, unwashed vegetables/fruits and contact with cats. Out of the 213 primary studies meta-analysed, raw/rare meats was enquired in 114 studies, unwashed vegetables/fruits in 41 studies and contact with cats in 156 studies. Thus, it was considered appropriate to perform separate meta-analysis on these three recurrent risk factors (Table 13).

Children who were fed with raw/rare beef or rare/raw non-specific meat (overall OR=1.223; 95% CI: 0.661 – 2.261) had, on average, a *numerically* lower risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis than both the mixed population (overall OR=1.758; 95% CI: 1.455 – 2.121) and the susceptible population (overall OR=1.808; 95% CI: 1.526 – 2.138) engaging in the same eating habits (Table 13). Statistically speaking, however, the three population types were at the same risk of acquiring the disease when consuming rare or raw meats. A forest plot of the OR association measures between toxoplasmosis and the ingestion of raw/rare meats in the

mixed and children population is shown in Figure 16, while one exclusively for the susceptible population is presented in Figure 17.

Table 13. Meta-analyses on the consumption of raw/rare meats (n=186), consumption of unwashed vegetables/fruits (n=63) and contact with cats (n=340) as risk factors for the transmission of toxoplasmosis – no geographical region removed

Exposure	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Raw/rare beef & non-specific meats (114 stud)	Fixed effects						
	Children	0.201 ^a	0.314	11	[-0.414 – 0.816]	0.522	
	Mixed	0.564 ^a	0.096	77	[0.375 – 0.752]	<.0001	
	Susceptible	0.592 ^a	0.086	98	[0.423 – 0.760]	<.0001	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2836	QE(df=183)		QM(df=3)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.5922	p<.0001		p=0.268		
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001		0.002		
	Points removed	0					
	Unwashed fruits & vgs (41 stud)	Fixed effects					
Mixed		0.560 ^a	0.126	39	[0.313 – 0.806]	<.0001	
Susceptible		0.478 ^a	0.152	24	[0.179 – 0.777]	0.002	
Random effects							
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.1573	QE(df=61)		QM(df=2)		
s^2 (residual)		0.4365	p<.0001		p=0.678		
Publication bias		0.0001	0.0002		0.566		
Points removed		0					
Contact with cats (156 stud)		Fixed effects					
		Children	0.479 ^a	0.126	51	[0.232 – 0.726]	<.0001
	Mixed	0.543 ^a	0.062	115	[0.422 – 0.664]	<.0001	
	Susceptible	0.567 ^a	0.057	174	[0.454 – 0.680]	<.0001	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2206	QE(df=337)		QM(df=3)		
	s^2 (residual)	0.5502	p<.0001		p=0.273		
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000		0.005		
	Points removed	0					

On meta-analysis, the mixed population (overall OR=1.751; 95% CI: 1.367 – 2.239) was as likely to acquire toxoplasmosis infection through the consumption of unwashed vegetables or fruits as the susceptible population (overall OR=1.612; 95% CI: 1.196 – 2.175; Table 13). Figure 18 shows a forest plot of the association between toxoplasmosis and consumption of unwashed vegetables/fruits for the combined mixed and susceptible population. Contact with cats was corroborated to be an important determinant of toxoplasmosis: statistically, children (overall OR=1.614; 95% CI: 1.261 – 2.067), the mixed population (overall OR=1.721; 95% CI: 1.525 – 1.942), and the susceptible population (overall OR=1.763; 95% CI: 1.575 – 1.974) were equally likely to acquire toxoplasmosis via contact with cats, although the risk was numerically higher in the susceptible population (Table 13). A forest plot of the association between toxoplasmosis and contact with cats in the mixed population is shown in Figure 19. For the susceptible population, due to the large number of observations (n=174), the meta-analysis could not be graphically represented by a forest plot. Instead, the Galbraith radial plot was used for display (Figure 20). Although the observations within the funnel plots for each of the three meta-analyses were quite homogeneously spread (Figure 15), the formal assessment of publication bias suggested that probably some OR estimates failing to determine a strong association of toxoplasmosis with raw/rare beef (p=0.002), and with contact with cats (p=0.005) remained unpublished (Table 13).

Figure 15. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses on the consumption of raw/rare meats (top left), the consumption of unwashed vegetables and fruits (top right) and contact with cats (bottom) as risk factors for the transmission of toxoplasmosis. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Figure 16. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between toxoplasmosis and consumption of raw/rare beef/non-specific meat in the combined mixed and children population (n=88) ordered by country

Figure 17. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between toxoplasmosis and consumption of raw/rare beef/non-specific meat in the susceptible population (n=98) ordered by country

Figure 18. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between toxoplasmosis and consumption of unwashed fruits/vegetables in the mixed and susceptible population (n=63) ordered by country

Figure 19. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between toxoplasmosis and contact with cats in the mixed population (n=115) ordered by country

Figure 20. Galbraith or radial plot of the meta-analysis on the association between toxoplasmosis and contact with cats in the susceptible population (n=174)

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled by means of four forest plots: the first forest plot was designed for comparing among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of toxoplasmosis in the mixed, susceptible and children population (Figure 21) and the other three forest plots for comparing among the *disaggregated* risk categories and specific pathways of exposure, separately presented for the mixed population (Figure 22), children (Figure 23) and susceptible population (Figure 24). To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Examining the global categories (Figure 21), the common most important global risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis was the set of host-specific factors in the mixed population (overall OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.53 – 2.12), children (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.01 – 2.57) and susceptible population (overall OR=1.87; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.40). In the mixed population, certain food categories, namely, seafood (overall OR=1.79; 95% CI: 1.02 – 3.14), produce (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.49 – 2.14) and meats (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.54 – 1.99) posed at least an equivalent level of risk of toxoplasmosis as the animal-related pathways of transmission (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.48 – 1.99), but a discernably higher level of risk than the environmental pathways as a whole (overall OR=1.54; 95% CI: 1.39 – 1.70). A comparable trend was observed in the global categories of the susceptible population: consumption of meat (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.52 – 1.99) conveyed a higher risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis than all animal pathways (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 1.49 – 1.83), followed by all environmental routes (overall OR=1.56; 95% CI: 1.38 – 1.76). However, in children, the opposite occurred: the environmental pathways (overall OR=1.70; 95% CI: 1.33 – 2.17) and contact with animals (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.28 – 1.96) were more

important vehicles of transmission than any food (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.63), specifically meat (overall OR=1.46; 95% CI: 1.18 – 1.81).

Figure 21. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

The global food categories that, on meta-analysis, came up as important vehicles of transmission of toxoplasmosis were (Figure 21): dairy in the mixed population (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.01 – 1.70); produce (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.16 – 1.71), raw eggs (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.22) and dairy (overall OR=1.26; 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.60) in the susceptible population; and dairy in children (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.92 – 1.71). Global categories that, on meta-analysis, were either minor or had a weak/non-significant association with *Toxoplasma gondii* infection were: multi-ingredient foods (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.16), raw eggs (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.00) and travel (overall OR=0.86; 95% CI: 0.70 – 1.05) in the mixed population; beverages (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.49 – 3.84) and multi-ingredient foods (overall OR=1.30; 95% CI: 0.87 – 1.97) in the susceptible population; and produce in children (overall OR=0.90; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.08; Figure 21).

Zooming into the disaggregated risk factors for toxoplasmosis, it became evident that poor personal hygiene habits (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.13 – 5.85), suffering from an immunocompromising condition or any other chronic disease (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.55), occupational contact with live/dead animals (overall OR=2.01; 95% CI: 1.65 – 2.45) and contact with soil (overall OR=1.93; 95% CI: 1.49 – 2.51) were the foremost risk factors for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (Figure 22). In the mixed population, consumption of foods such as raw molluscs (in Asian studies; overall OR=1.95; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.65), pork (overall OR=1.84; 95% CI: 1.32 – 2.55), fresh vegetables (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.48 – 2.22), red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.42 – 2.30), raw/rare beef/non-specific meats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.45 – 2.12), unwashed fruits and vegetables (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.37 – 2.24) and other meats (overall OR=1.73; 95% CI: 1.52 – 1.97) presented a level of risk of toxoplasmosis comparable (if not, higher) to that of the most known source of toxoplasmosis, contact with cats (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.53 – 1.94) or pets in general (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.45 – 1.96). At a lower association with toxoplasmosis, yet still significant, laid the environmental routes of untreated drink water (overall OR=1.68; 95% CI: 1.28 – 2.19), farm environment (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.25 – 2.14) and exposure to waste water or human waste (overall OR=1.55; 95% CI: 0.85 – 2.84); followed by the other animal-related pathways of contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.47; 95% CI: 1.19 – 1.81) and farm animals (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.00). Food vehicles found to pose a lower risk of transmission of toxoplasmosis were: beef meat, mostly undercooked (overall OR=1.48; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.00), poultry meat (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.03), unwashed fruits (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.84 – 2.24), raw milk (overall OR=1.27; 95% CI: 1.03 – 1.58) and processed meat (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.93 – 1.65). In the mixed population (Figure 22), routes of exposures likely to be minor sources of toxoplasmosis, or weakly associated with the disease, were: person-to-person contagion (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 0.57 – 4.73), recreational water (overall OR=1.33; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.59), milk products (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.81), raw eggs (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.00), fish (overall OR=1.04; 95% CI: 0.76 – 1.41), composite dishes (overall OR=0.93; 95% CI: 0.52 – 1.67), domestic travel (overall OR=0.89; 95% CI: 0.69 – 1.15) and international travel (overall OR=0.69; 95% CI: 0.48 – 1.00).

Figure 22. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis in the mixed population for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

In the children population (Figure 23), the top three determinants of toxoplasmosis were: consumption of rare pork/cured meat (overall OR=2.19; 95% CI: 1.34 – 5.85), keeping poor hygiene habits – a top risk factor that came up also in the mixed population (overall OR=2.06; 95% CI: 0.82 – 5.17) and living on a farm (overall OR=2.02; 95% CI: 1.70 – 2.39), all of which posed a higher level of risk than the best known source of toxoplasmosis, contact with cats (overall OR=1.63; 95% CI: 1.31 – 2.03) or any pet (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.26 – 2.07). Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children were: exposure to human waste (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.34 – 1.83), suffering from medical conditions (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.91 – 2.52), contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.87), other (non-classifiable) meats (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 0.94 – 2.08),

untreated drink water (overall OR=1.38; 95% CI: 1.20 – 1.59), contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.81) and contact with soil (viz. playground; overall OR=1.13; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.30). The least important routes of transmission of toxoplasmosis (i.e., deemed as such for having either OR<1.0 or non-significant p-values) related all to food pathways, and these were red meats (overall OR=1.28; 95% CI: 0.57 – 2.84), milk (overall OR=1.24; 95% CI: 0.78 – 1.97), raw/rare meats (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.66 – 2.26), raw vegetables (overall OR=0.87; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.03) and poultry meat (overall OR=0.73; 95% CI: 0.28 – 1.92).

Figure 23. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis in the children population for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

In the susceptible population, the top three determinants of toxoplasmosis were: suffering from a medical condition (overall OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.76 – 3.00), consuming beef – mostly undercooked (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.44 – 3.09) and being exposed to waste water or human waste (overall OR=1.88; 95% CI: 1.18 – 3.01; Figure 24). Consuming red meats,

mostly of wild nature (overall OR=1.86; 95% CI: 1.31 – 2.65) was as risky an eating habit in pregnant women as consuming any raw/rare meat (overall OR=1.81; 95% CI: 1.52 – 2.14), while having occupational contact with live/dead animals (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 1.29 – 2.44) was as unsafe as having contact with cats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.57 – 1.97).

Figure 24. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

Consuming other (non-classifiable) meats (overall OR=1.76; 95% CI: 1.50 – 2.06), living on a farm (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.15), and having contact with any pets (overall OR=1.66; 95% CI: 1.46 – 1.87) were at least as strong determinants of toxoplasmosis as international travel (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.53), pork meat (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.53), unwashed fruits and vegetables (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.20 – 2.17), poultry meat (overall OR=1.60; 95% CI: 1.08 – 2.37), processed meats (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.32), fruits (overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.06 – 2.22) and contact with soil (overall OR=1.49; 95% CI: 1.33 – 1.66). Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population, although at a lower level of association, were: consumption of raw eggs (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.22), suffering from a chronic disease (overall OR=1.42; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.12), drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.40;

95% CI: 1.21 – 1.61), contact with wild animals (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.95 – 1.95), and consumption of raw milk (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI: 1.07 – 1.67) and vegetables (overall OR=1.30; 95% CI: 1.13 – 1.49). Unlike the mixed population, composite dishes eaten out represented a risky practice in the susceptible population (overall OR=1.23; 95% CI: 0.94 – 1.63). Minor (or non-significant) pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population were (Figure 24): recent use of antibiotics (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.63 – 2.51), consuming cheese (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.61 – 1.58), contact with farm animals (overall OR=0.93; 95% CI: 0.67 – 1.31) and exposure to recreational water (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.53 – 1.03). It is worthy to highlight that, in the susceptible population, the minor pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis were fewer (only four) than those of the mixed population (eight) and children (five). Said otherwise, in the susceptible population – predominantly pregnant women, most of the potential sources of toxoplasmosis under study turned out to be statistically significant.

3.8.4 *Meta-analysis on the effect of handling food on the risk of transmission of toxoplasmosis*

The only food data partitions comprising sufficient data that could support the assessment of the effect of handling (i.e., raw, undercooked and unwashed) were those of meat, vegetables and dairy. Full estimates and funnel plots of the meta-analysis on the effects of handling are shown in the supplementary Tables S1, S2, and S3 and Figures S1, S2, and S3, respectively. For the toxoplasmosis meta-analysis, no data partition had sufficient information on setting; thus, the effect of eating food prepared outside the home on the overall association with disease could not be appraised. However, recall that most of the data on composite foods – dishes – had the common feature of having been prepared outside, so the pooled OR estimate for dishes can be approximated to the setting “eating out”.

Table 14. Meta-analysed effects of handling on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Beef, poultry, pork, other red meats, non-specific meats	OR(Base)	1.584	1.363	1.839
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.253	0.996	1.576
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.084	0.897	1.313
Fruits & vegs	OR(Base)	1.219	0.992	1.499
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.157	0.905	1.480
	OR(Unwashed)/OR(Base)	1.465	1.179	1.820
Milk & cheese	OR(Base)	1.027	0.885	1.191
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.414	1.062	1.850

On meta-analysis, people who ate beef, poultry, pork, other red meats or any non-specific meat and became ill with toxoplasmosis were 1.253 times (95% CI: 0.996 – 1.576) more likely to have consumed it raw than those who had the same type of meat but did not acquire

the disease. As a whole, both types of preparation, raw and undercooked, increased the risk level, although it was only marginal when meat was undercooked (~1.084 times; 95% CI: 0.897 – 1.313; Table 14). On the other hand, not washing vegetables prior to consumption increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis by 1.465 (95% CI: 1.179 – 1.820), which was significantly higher than that of eating vegetables in raw state (risk increased by 1.157; 95% CI: 0.905 – 1.480). In other words, people who ate fresh vegetables and became ill were more likely to have consumed them unwashed (~1.5 times) than to have consumed them raw (~1.2 times, than those who consumed fresh vegetables but did not get ill. Hence, the practice of not washing vegetables before consumption bears a significant risk of toxoplasmosis on its own (p=0.001; Table S2). In relation to the milk and cheese data partition, the meta-analysis on handling effect revealed that milk or cheese was not a significant route of transmission of toxoplasmosis (p=0.726; Table S3). However, when non-pasteurised milk or cheese was consumed, the risk became significant (p=0.017; Table S3). Thus, on meta-analysis, people who consumed milk/cheese and acquired toxoplasmosis were ~1.414 times (95% CI: 1.062 – 1.850) more likely to have consumed unpasteurised products than those who consumed milk/cheese but did not get the disease (Table 14).

3.8.5 Synthesis of the risks associated to preparation practices and poor handling of foods

The forest plot of Figure 25 compiles exposures related to food preparation, which were examined as potential risk factors for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population. While washing vegetables with salt or any disinfectant may even confer some protective effect against toxoplasmosis (ORs: 0.51 – 0.64), the habit of tasting raw meat while cooking is seemingly a risky preparation practice in susceptible people (ORs: 1.01 and 5.60). Cooking with microwave might also pose some risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis (OR=1.30), particularly if resulting meats are not fully cooked.

Figure 25. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis associated to food preparation practices in the susceptible population

Most of the poor food handling habits explored in the primary studies related to hand hygiene and infrequent cleaning of knives and other utensils while cooking (Figure 26). Odds-ratios for infrequent handwashing as a potential determinant of toxoplasmosis were, in most cases, significant and ranged between 1.56 and 9.90 in the susceptible population. In the susceptible population, significant ORs were also associated to potential cross-contaminating practices such as infrequent washing of knives or other utensils (ORs: 1.19 – 7.30) and not washing knives after cutting raw meat/vegetables (ORs: 1.0 – 2.7). In the mixed population, all of the poor food handling practices retrieved from the cohort studies related to hands hygiene: while not washing hands before cooking presented a high OR (7.14), not washing hands before eating bore a variable association with toxoplasmosis (ORs: 0.91 – 10.0). However, not washing hands after handling raw meat or eating with bare hands could not be proven to be determinant of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring toxoplasmosis associated to poor food handling practices in the susceptible and mixed population

4 Conclusions

4.8 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic toxoplasmosis

- ❖ The outcomes from 213 cohort and case-control studies investigating host-specific factors and pathways of transmission for sporadic toxoplasmosis were meta-analysed within appropriate data partitions, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ The host-specific factors, as globally meta-analysed, constituted the most important risk factor for acquiring toxoplasmosis in the three population types: mixed (OR=1.80), children (OR=1.61) and susceptible (OR=1.87).
- ❖ In the mixed and susceptible population, food as a whole – in particular meat – was a stronger determinant of toxoplasmosis than environmental routes, followed by animal-related routes. In children, on the contrary, the environmental and animal contact routes were more important sources of toxoplasmosis than the food vehicles.
- ❖ The top four determinants of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population were: poor personal hygiene habits (OR=2.57), suffering from a chronic disease (OR=2.07), occupational contact with animals (OR=2.01) and contact with soil (overall OR).
- ❖ In the mixed population, consumption of raw molluscs (in Asia, OR=1.95), pork (OR=1.84), fresh vegetables (OR=1.81), red meats other than beef (OR=1.81), raw or rare beef/non-specific meats (OR=1.76), unwashed fruits and vegetables (OR=1.75) and other meats (OR=1.73) presented a level of risk of toxoplasmosis comparable to (if not, higher than) that of contact with cats (OR=1.72) or any pet (OR=1.69).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the aforementioned food sources were stronger determinants of disease than the environmental routes of untreated drink water (OR=1.68), farm environment (OR=1.64) and exposure to waste (OR=1.55); followed by the animal-related pathways of contact with wild animals (OR=1.47) and farm animals (OR=1.43).
- ❖ Food vehicles bearing the lowest risk of transmission of toxoplasmosis in the mixed population were: beef meat (OR=1.48), poultry meat (OR=1.45), unwashed fruits (OR=1.37), raw milk (OR=1.27) and processed meat (OR=1.24).
- ❖ In the mixed population, routes of exposure that had the weakest or no association with toxoplasmosis were: person-to-person contagion (OR=1.65), recreational water (OR=1.33), milk products (OR=1.17), raw eggs (OR=1.17), fish (OR=1.04), composite dishes (OR=0.93), domestic travel (OR=0.89) and international travel (OR=0.69).

- ❖ In children, the top three determinants of toxoplasmosis were: consumption of rare pork/cured meat (OR=2.19), keeping poor hygiene habits (OR=2.06) and living on a farm (overall OR=2.02; 95% CI: 1.70 – 2.39), all of which posed a higher level of risk than contact with cats (OR=1.63) or any pet (OR=1.61).
- ❖ Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children were: exposure to human waste (OR=1.57), suffering from medical conditions (OR=1.51), contact with wild animals (OR=1.41), other (non-classifiable) meats (OR=1.40), untreated drink water (OR=1.38), contact with farm animals (OR=1.24) and contact with soil (OR=1.13).
- ❖ Minor pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in children were all related to food, namely, red meats (OR=1.28), milk (OR=1.24), raw/rare meats (OR=1.22), raw vegetables (OR=0.87) and poultry meat (OR=0.73).
- ❖ In the susceptible population, the top three determinants of toxoplasmosis were: suffering from a medical condition (OR=2.30), consuming undercooked beef (OR=2.11) and being exposed to human waste (OR=1.88).
- ❖ Consuming red meats, mostly of wild nature (OR=1.86) was as risky an eating habit in pregnant women as consuming any raw/rare meat (OR=1.81), while having occupational contact with animals (OR=1.78) was as risky as having contact with cats (OR=1.76).
- ❖ Other (non-classifiable) meats (OR=1.76), living on a farm (OR=1.75), and contact with any pets (OR=1.66) were at least as strong determinants of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population as international travel (OR=1.64), pork meat (OR=1.64), unwashed fruits and vegetables (OR=1.61), poultry meat (OR=1.60), processed meats (OR=1.59), fruits (OR=1.53) and contact with soil (OR=1.49).
- ❖ Other significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population were: raw eggs (OR=1.45), chronic disease (OR=1.42), untreated drink water (OR=1.40), contact with wild animals (OR=1.36), and consumption of raw milk (OR=1.34) and vegetables (OR=1.30).
- ❖ Unlike the mixed population, composite dishes eaten out can represent a risky practice in the susceptible population (OR=1.23).
- ❖ Minor or non-significant pathways of transmission of toxoplasmosis in the susceptible population were: recent use of antibiotics (OR=1.25), cheese (OR=0.98), contact with farm animals (OR=0.93) and exposure to recreational water (OR=0.74).
- ❖ Eating raw meat increased the probability of acquiring toxoplasmosis by 1.25 times while eating undercooked meat marginally increased the odds of infection by 1.08 times that of eating “simply” meat.

- ❖ Consuming vegetables without washing them increased the risk of acquiring toxoplasmosis by 1.47, which was significantly higher than that of eating vegetables in raw state (1.16 times higher).
- ❖ Consuming non-pasteurised milk or raw milk cheese conveyed an increased risk of toxoplasmosis, quantified as 1.414 times that of consuming milk/cheese.

5 References

5.8 Two-hundred and thirteen cohort and case-control primary studies assessing risk factors for toxoplasmosis

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6 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling on the transmission of toxoplasmosis

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of beef (n=56), poultry (n=44), pork (n=52), other red meats (n=89) or non-classified meats (n=293) in the combined mixed (n=253), children (n=19) and susceptible (n=262) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All (145 stud)	Base	0.460	0.076	304	[0.310 – 0.609]	<.0001
	Raw	0.226	0.117	83	[-0.004 – 0.455]	0.054
	Undercooked	0.081	0.097	147	[-0.109 – 0.272]	0.404
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2695	QE(df=531)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.7325	p<.0001		p=0.157	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001			<.0001
	Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of beef, poultry, pork, other red meats or non-classified meats. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of fruits (n=17) and vegetables (n=123) in the combined mixed (n=68), children (n=8) and susceptible (n=64) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Both (83 stud)	Base	0.198	0.105	28	[-0.008 – 0.405]	0.059
	Raw	0.146	0.125	49	[-0.100 – 0.392]	0.243
	Unwashed	0.382	0.111	63	[0.165 – 0.599]	0.001
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1784	QE(df=137)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3976	p<.0001		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.613
	Points removed	0				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of fruits and vegetables. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S3. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of milk (n=66) and cheese (n=8) in the combined mixed (n=26), children (n=4) and susceptible (n=44) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Both (48 stud)	Base	0.027	0.076	20	[-0.122 – 0.175]	0.726
	Raw	0.337	0.141	54	[0.060 – 0.615]	0.017
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2995	QE(df=72)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3466	p<.0001		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.139
	Points removed	0				

Figure S3. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis on the effect of handling on the risk of toxoplasmosis by consumption of milk and cheese. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias